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EDITORIAL

Ricardo De Bonis,
CEO – Instituto iiEP
PhD, MBA, DDS

The journal IJEReseearch-International Journal of Education and Research, in its second edition, reflects the effort of the Instituto iiEP team to organize a journal that manages to have a greater reach. The publication in English, the language most used for the dissemination of scientific studies, makes us believe that we will be able to draw attention to our journal, exalting the quality of our research. Obeying the ethics of scientific communication, exploring the linguistic resources that language allows. Originality is another important point in scientific dissemination, as innovation fits into any discussion. Therefore, IJEReseearch is committed to always presenting the new and the current. I thank the authors who sent us the articles to be published.

Rio de Janeiro, December 30, 2021

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ACCEPTANCE, FAMILY AND RESPECT – THE SEARCH WAS NEVER FOR TOLERANCE. AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW APPLIED TO PUBLIC HEALTH

Author: Romero Vieira Vasconcelos

ABSTRACT : Even today, homosexuality is a controversial subject, generating diverse opinions among scholars in the area, in which it is possible to identify the existing risks and barriers that homosexual faces when revealing his homosexuality in the family and social sphere, since many times there may be negative consequences, such as family contempt, depression, homophobia, among others. The objective of the present study is to identify and describe the scientific evidence about family and social acceptance regarding homosexual orientation. It is an integrative review of literature in the scielo , lilacs and bdenf databases, presenting researches between the period from 1999 to 2017. The results point out the difficulties of accepting the family and the society when it comes to homosexuality, and can generate internal and external conflicts when not in this respect, the consequences can generate harm to the homosexual such as risk of suffering homophobia, prejudice, rejection by various environments.

Keywords: Homosexuality. Family relationships. Tolerance.

INTRODUCTION

To talk about homosexuality, it must be necessary to talk about sexuality, whose concept is a little complicated, as it involves a series of factors, such as behavior, the sexual act, notions of what is masculine and feminine and sexual orientation, the latter being the theme of the present work.

Homosexuality in ancient Greece and Rome was considered natural, as there was already the existence of homosexual relationships, where the cult of beauty was practiced in which older men gathered in a gymnasium to appreciate the physical beauty of young people who remained naked. However, it was not called homosexuality, because what predominated was bisexuality, since men joined women in order to reproduce, in which heterosexual relationships began to predominate, and then marriage and family emerged (MOREIRA, MARTINS, 2008).

With the end of the Roman Empire in 533 BC with Justinian there was a complete change in the direction of homosexuality, where it was punished with burning and castration, claiming that homosexual practice was not a practice accepted by God. Thus arising the non-acceptance of male homosexuality.

It is justified that, for a better understanding of homosexuality, the definition of sexual orientation is distinguished, which is the ability to develop, have or feel attraction or sexual, emotional or affective relationship with other people. Being subdivided into: Heterosexual: person who feels attraction or relates to people of the opposite sex. Bisexual: A person who is attracted to or has relationships with people of both sexes. Homosexual: person who is attracted to or has relationships with people of the same sex, where homosexual women are called lesbians, homosexual men are called gays. (BRAZIL, 2016).

The International Association of Gays, Lesbians, Bisexuals, Transsexuals and Intersexuals (ILGA), reinforce that the definition for homophobia is fear, aversion or discrimination against homosexuality, being also characterized as hatred, hostility or disapproval of the same. In 2007, around

85 member states of the United Nations still criminalize homosexual relationships, making the culture of hate official, where the homosexual population needs to hide out of fear, in which the prevailing culture related to hate and violence are accepted by the state, forcing this population into invisibility and self-denial (OTTOSSON, 2007).

In 1894, the term Homosexuality was used for the first time in Brazil by Francisco José Viveiros de Castro in the book "indecent assault: studies on aberrations of the sexual instinct". In the late 1970s and early 1980s, during the military dictatorship, social movements marked history not only in the search for democracy but for civil rights and citizenship, thus starting the construction of movements, also making visible the construction of gay movements.

With this, the first gay movement in Brazil emerged in 1979 in São Paulo and the first Brazilian meeting of homosexuals was held the following year. Starting an incessant fight for the end of discrimination and prejudice, that is, a fight against the so ingrained homophobia present visibly and invisibly in our society (PAGANO, 2011).

As a problem, it is seen that, despite the difficulties in finding statistical data, studies indicate that the percentage of homosexuals is represented by about 3% to 10% of the population (NOGUEIRA et al., 2012). In Brazil there are more than 60 thousand homosexual couples, whose region with the most homosexual couples is the Southeast, totaling 32,202 couples, followed by the Northeast with 12,196 couples. The South region has just over 8,000 homosexual couples, the Midwest with 4,141. And finally, the North region with the lowest number of homosexual couples totaled 3,429. (BRAZIL, 2010).

Despite advances in studies, homosexuality is still seen today as a sin, disease and crime, thus generating great rejection, discrimination from family members and society, people with homosexual orientation are found in all social environments, including socioeconomic groups, ethical and religious (MAGRINI et al., 2014).

People who are part of these groups of sexual diversity become frequent victims of prejudice and discrimination due to their choice of gender identity and/or sexual orientation. Homophobia, a term used to define the prejudice of those who are against homosexuality, is mainly marked by aggressive gestures, offensive words, looks and even physical aggression and murders. This act is considered as unhealthy hatred (PAGANO, 2011).

One of the main difficulties in relation to homophobia when it is present in the family, making it complex in some cases for the homosexual to reveal his orientation (ZUCCHI; GARCIA, 1999).

Faced with this question, there is the question of the problem: What scientific evidence about family and social acceptance of homosexual orientation ?

As a hypothesis, it is seen that when assuming homosexuality, the individual needs mainly family support, however, in some cases it ends up being more difficult , thus leading to a destabilization and distance from family members, sometimes causing the gay to end up in search of new family references, such as the family of friends for feeling rejected by their own family (GONSALVES; SILVA, 2013).

Parenteral rejection, acceptance difficulties and bullying are responsible for at least one third of adolescent suicide deaths related to orientation issues (NOGUEIRA et al., 2012).

Therefore, the objective of this article is to identify the scientific evidence about family and social acceptance of homosexual orientation . The specific objectives are to write the scientific evidence about family acceptance of the individual's sexual orientation ; to verify the challenges faced by homosexuals in the family environment; and finally, to analyze what kind of family and social acceptance of the homosexual orientation.

A problem of investigation, at times, is drawn from what was evidenced in the review of studies on the difficulty of accepting the family in homosexuality. Showing the

consequences for family rejection and society in general.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The integrative review According to Soares et al., (2014) is considered a form of systematic review, it consists of a broad analysis of publications, in order to obtain data on a given topic. This type of research includes the analysis of relevant publications, allows the synthesis of published studies on the subject, can indicate knowledge gaps that need to be filled through new research, in addition to providing general conclusions regarding the area of study. In order to maintain standards of methodological rigor, some steps were followed.

The first was the delimitation of the research question, the second was the choice of databases, the third step was the selection of these studies for this, key information was extracted, considering the question proposed for the investigation, in addition to identifying the type of study, subjects involved in the research, the scenario and the objectives, for the conclusion of this stage and the formulation of the results of this review, it was decided to use spreadsheets in Microsoft Excel , in order to gather and systematize this information. The other steps or steps were: analysis of included studies and interpretation of results. Once the methodological steps for this type of study were defined, they were followed as follows:

- 1) Starting from the need to explore studies in national and international scientific literature with the proposed research question: family acceptance and society's respect for homosexuals?

- 2) As for sampling or search, this IR counted as inclusion criteria studies published with a time frame from 1999 to 2017. Justified because in 1999, resolution 01/99 was created, which defines the attitude of psychologists as unethical who treat homosexuality as a deviant behavior and disease.

For selection, we opted for articles with full texts, preferably published in scientific journals of Nursing, methodology containing the necessary data to obtain the levels of evidence and being a research with emphasis on the research question. As exclusion criteria, publications unavailable in full text or inaccessible link due to error and other forms of publication other than scientific articles were chosen.

Articles that do not parallel the research topic were also excluded. Review articles and experience reports were not used in this research. This fact constituted a limitation of the study, as some relevant subjects could be contained in these other types of publications, such as monographs, editorials, manuals, books, among others. Searches were restricted to the following descriptors: Homosexuality; Family, acceptance, rejection and homophobia.

This IR presents primary research on the topic addressed, we chose to carry out searches in journals indexed in the databases and libraries of: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO), Latin American and Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences (LILACS), Nursing Database (BDENF).

Initially, for the first round of searches, it was decided to cross the descriptor homosexuality and the words family is nursing, a total of 96 articles were found, 28 articles in SCIELO, 60 in LILACS, 8 in BDENF.

Continuing with the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we initially excluded 58 articles from the search, details shown in Table 01.

Table 01: Application of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

STAGE	CRITERIA / BASES	SCIELO	LILACS	BDENF
1	Descriptors used in the search	Homosexuality Family	Homosexuality Family	Homosexuality Nursing
two	Articles found	28	60	8
3	Articles with a year of publication prior to 1999	0	7	1
4	Full texts available	27	37	6
5	Repeated / Duplicate Articles	0	0	0

6	Experience reports and review articles	0	two	two
7	Articles outside the research topic	7	14	0
8	Total articles excluded	8	46	4
9	Total viable articles for next step	20	14	4

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2017.

It should be noted that after step three, a previous reading was carried out, where a total of 28 articles from the research were excluded at this stage, as they did not fit the search question and the scope of this research. For analysis and next steps, 10 articles were selected. Table 02 presents the composition of the sample.

Table 02: Composition of the sample – Characterization of the studies by: title, descriptors, year and place of publication.

TITLE	DESCRIPTORS	PLACE / YEAR
The Debate on Homosexuality Mediated by Social Representations: Homosexual and Heterosexual Perspectives.	Homosexuality; social representations; social recognition; causality.	Rio de Janeiro-RJ / 2006
Life trajectory of a homosexual: between silence and oppression.	Homosexuality. Sexual behavior. Nursing assessment research. Community health nursing. Nursing	Natal-RN / 2007
Personal and family experiences of female homosexuals.	Female homosexuality, personal and family experiences.	Maringá-PR / 2008
Sexuality and work: study on the discrimination of male homosexuals in the banking sector.	Discrimination, male homosexuals, public bank, private bank.	São Paulo-SP / 2010
Humanization in the reception of lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transvestites and transsexuals in primary care: bioethical reflections.	Reception; primary care; homosexuality; bioethics.	Recife-PE 2011
Suicide Ideas and Attempts in Adolescents with Hetero and Homoerotic Sexual Practices.	Homophobia; Suicide; Homosexuality; Adolescence; sexual identity; Violence.	São Paulo-SP / 2012
Family and sexual orientation: Difficulties in accepting male homosexuality.	Homosexuality, family, sexual orientation.	Barretos-SP / 2014
Between revealing and hiding: parents and children in the face of the discovery of homosexuality.	Young homosexuals; family; domestic violence, Brazil.	Rio de Janeiro-RJ / 2014
Mothers, Children and Homosexuality: Narratives of Acceptance.	Homosexuality, acceptance, son, mother.	Irati-PR / 2015
The impact of homophobia on the health of homosexual adolescents.	Adolescent Health. Violence. Homosexuality.	Ribeirão Preto-SP / 2015

Source: Prepared by the authors .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proceeding with the presentation of the results of the selected publications, it was observed that most studies have a qualitative methodological approach in a total of 10 articles. The research attention scenario presented variation, the family scenario stands out, however, the social scenario is punctuated as something emerging.

As for the country of origin of the studies, Brazil was the highlight hosting the 10 studies. As for the year of publication, there is a greater concentration of articles in the year 2014 and 2015, with 2 publications each.

The most prominent journal in the area was: *Temas em Psicologia* with two articles. The other journals had one publication each.

As for the objective of the articles, most of them point to family acceptance, as shown in Table 01. In this perspective, the authors emphasize that the complete acceptance of parents towards children with homosexual orientation does not apply in all cases, given that for most homosexual people this acceptance is something out of their reality because it is not an easy transition on either side. After the revelation, the parents faced six stages, namely: discovery, mourning, denial, defense, conformation and, in some cases, acceptance (HAUER, SIQUEIRA, 2015).

Table 3 : Distribution of articles by author, objective and journal, on family acceptance and society's respect for homosexuals: an integrative review with implications for nursing.

AUTHOR/YEAR	OBJECTIVE	PERIODICAL
Scardua ; alves, (2006)	To study the representations of homosexuality among university students, according to sexual orientation and sex.	Psychology: Reflection and Criticism.
Albino et al., (2007)	Unveiling the world of the person affected by a sexually transmitted disease, more specifically in investigating the life trajectory of a homosexual.	Science, Care and Health.
Arial ; centenary, (2008)	To describe the personal and family experiences of female homosexuals.	Psychology in Study.
Garcia; Moulin, (2010)	To analyze possible forms of discrimination in the workplace directed towards homosexual male employees.	Public Administration Magazine.

Souza et al., (2011)	Reflect on how public health can use the Bioethics framework to base its practice and assistance in relation to ensuring a humanized reception for Lesbians, Gays, Bisexuals, Transvestites and Transsexuals (LGBT) in primary care health services.	UFPE nursing journal online.
Silva; Rondini, (2012)	It sought to know the associations between sexual orientation and suicide ideations and attempts.	Health and society.
Magrini, et al., (2014)	To understand the experience of men with homosexual orientation and the construction of the meanings of homosexuality in their respective families of origin.	Subjects in Psychology.
Barcelona; Baptist, (2014)	It deals with the relationship between parents and children when faced with the social situation of the discovery of homosexuality.	Latin American Magazine.
Hauer; Siqueira, (2015)	Understand how the process of acceptance of a homosexual son or daughter by his mother takes place.	Subjects in Psychology.
Regis et al., (2015)	Understand how homophobia can influence the health of homosexual adolescents.	Anna Nery School.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2017.

After a thorough reading and data collection of the articles included in the IR, we identified that:

There are indications that homosexuality has been present in the history of humanity and since primitive societies in all cultures. In which the first reports appeared around the third Egyptian dynasty, around 2,500 BC. At the time, some civilizations allowed relationships between men, adults and young people, as it was only considered repudiation when they threatened to subvert the social hierarchy. Over time, this situation was explained in different ways. However, with the arrival of the Judeo-Christian tradition, homosexuality was changed, starting to be conceived as a sin (ARIAL; CENTENARO, 2008).

In view of the religious situation, the practices considered homo-affective were highlighted by the bible, both in the Old and New Testaments, where these biblical texts refer to the manifestations of human sexuality, in which the texts only emphasize evidence regarding the male sexual option (ALBINO et al., 2007).

Each person has their sexuality constructed through biopsychosocial aspects, which are divided into four pillars, biological sex as male and female, sexual identity defined as male and female, sexual orientation being homosexual, heterosexual and bisexual, it is the psychological aspect being understood by behaviors, attitudes and feelings, identified in the third pillar of the biopsychosocial aspects, sexual orientation and understood individually by the desire of each being throughout life, this desire being represented as heterosexual: attraction to the opposite sex. Bisexual: attraction to both sexes. Homosexual: attraction to people of the same sex. Where there is a need to be accepted, recognized and understood in their specificities and social and family relationships (MAGRINI et al., 2014).

The term homosexuality, which is widely used today, originated in German in a pamphlet considered anonymous in 1869 (ALBINO et al., 2007).

However, from the 19th century onwards homosexuality was defined by doctors as a physiological disease, in the 20th century it came to be seen by psychology as a behavioral deviation from sexuality due to the introduction of the suffix ISM. In which it came to be defined as a psychopathological disease where it was published in 1984 in the 6th journal of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), falling into the category of pathological personality. In Brazil, in the 1980s, the Federal Council of Medicine stopped classifying homosexuality as a category of deviation and sexual disorder, making code 302.0 of the international classification of diseases unusable.

In 1999, the federal council of psychology made official through resolution 01/99, in which the posture of psychologists who treat homosexuality as a behavioral deviation and disease is unethical, resulting in a decision by the World Health Organization (WHO), which stops considering homosexuality as a disease (ARRIAL, CENTENARO, 2008).

According to Hauer and Siqueira (2015), homosexuality is still seen with a certain repudiation even with the increase in social

visibility, causing greater difficulties mainly in the family environment, where the main part of the parents' desire when it comes to waiting for a child and that it is oriented as heterosexual, as it will be a "right and natural" gender. As a girl, she will wear pink, play with dolls and practice ballet, while the boy will wear blue, play with carts and attend soccer class, making it impossible for this orientation to be changed to homosexuality over the years.

Consequently, when parents are faced with a homosexual son or daughter, it ends up being something embarrassing for that family. Having as a consequence, the deviation of the plans prior to this revelation, generating then the fear of social and divine judgment where the family ends up looking for who to blame, thus generating parenteral homophobia.

Silva and Rondini (2012) reinforce that homosexuality has a different representation in each place, considering that revealing their homosexuality in the family and social context can result in several different situations, such as value and consequences.

Knowing that the "family of origin" has greater difficulty in accepting the homosexual orientation of their children, from then on it ends up generating a conflict on both sides, and actions of physical and verbal violence can occur. Being marked by fear, apprehension and uncertainty on both sides. There is also evidence of psychological violence that is experienced silently, causing serious damage to the victim, such as health problems, low performance and even suicide attempts (BARCELOS; BATISTA, 2014).

Many times the homosexual ends up being forced to live in society hiding their true sexual orientation, because they were raised by a heterosexist model, where parents end up inducing their children to believe that they will marry and form a family, making a search of a partner of the opposite sex so as not to go against the wishes of the parents. (SILVA; RONDINI, 2012).

In addition to family rejection, homosexuals also encounter barriers in society

through homophobia and discrimination. Homophobia is characterized by a set of negative symptoms, such as fear, annoyance, hatred and repudiation, and its forms of expression are through physical force, psychological, verbal and sexual aggression. Related to the power of gender in society. According to the Ministry of Health, in 2012, 4,851 cases of homophobia were registered, which demonstrates a problem of great magnitude in society. Being a homosexual teenager, the largest population considered vulnerable, because they are teenagers and because of the violence and exclusion they are exposed to (REGIS et al., 2015).

It is observed that prejudice and any form of negative mental perception towards individuals and socially inferior groups, as well as the social representations connected to such perceptions, which means the materialization in the concrete plane of relationships, which produce violation of the rights of individuals and groups related to homosexuals, the author states that most homosexuals tend to hide their sexuality in environments such as work, with the intention of avoiding any and all discriminatory acts. On the other hand, those who hide their sexual orientation manifest low psychological levels of well-being and life satisfaction (GARCIA; MOULIN, 2010).

Regis et al. (2015) emphasizes that male homosexuals are more prone to suffer any type of Physical or Verbal Violence or even homophobic acts than homosexual women, due to the heterosexist society, the main occurrences of homophobia and in school, family and social environments. The most prevalent and verbal violence in which society uses pejorative terms to offend homosexuals causing fear of exposing their sexuality, which often due to parenteral and social homophobia can result in suicide.

Finally, parenteral rejection, acceptance difficulties and bullying are responsible for at least one third of the deaths by suicide of adolescents in relation to sexual orientation issues, data from DATASUS indicate that in Brazil, for every 100,000 inhabitants between 15 and 19 years the suicide

mortality rate is 4 for men and 2 for women. However, men when trying to commit suicide are more successful compared to women, due to the typology of suicide, although women try more against life, thus observing that sexual orientation is related to suicide symptoms (SILVA; RODINI, 2012).

Sousa et al., (2011) states that the process of changing a person towards sexual orientation is not easy, in which the hegemonic heterosexual pattern predominates in professional assistance based on prejudice and discrimination, which can thus generate institutional homophobia and put at risk the rights of citizens, leading to the removal of health services for LGBT people. On the other hand, government policies have been fighting homophobia, where the general objective of the national LGBT health policy is to eliminate any and all forms of prejudice and discrimination, aiming to reduce inequality both in society and in the consolidation of the principles of SUS

Of the articles selected for research, most of them addressed the family environment and homosexuality as a central theme, with prejudice and homophobia being a background, or something directed in the background, or even just mentioned in the studies. It is emphasized here that, based on what was found, further discussion is needed through research on family and social acceptance of homosexuals as a real object of studies, emphasizing the risks of non-acceptance of homosexuality to the family and society, as the eradication of parenteral and social homophobia.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In view of the study presented, it is possible to conclude that homosexuality is known since the dawn of humanity, being studied from the beginning of the twentieth century, obtaining, then, several definitions until the present day. Over the years, homosexuals come in search of more space in society, even with several barriers faced.

It appears that one of the problems for confronting prejudice begins in the home environment itself, being in the vast

majority heterosexist. A barrier then occurs when the child decides to reveal his/her sexual orientation, as he/she is faced with an environment of rejection, the parents are faced with the “destruction” of the dream of a so-called traditional family. Thus, the first barrier for homosexuals to assume their gender identity arises. Added to family traditionalism we have the religious issue.

There are many obstacles to be faced by homosexuals, not just family rejection and in some cases religious intolerance, they still have to face a certain prejudice and homophobia sometimes veiled in part of society. Homophobia is demonstrated with verbal abuse, even generating physical aggression, which may have consequences without return, such as depression, suicide and homicide .

Homosexual acceptance is something that encompasses several difficulties, and homosexuals need support from health services, especially psychological support, in an attempt to face their internal and external conflicts.

Although homosexuality is currently a popular topic, no publications were found regarding nurses’ interventions in the context of homosexual acceptance, not even regarding differentiated reception for this public.

In relation to the researched studies, it is concluded that the specific intervention of the nurse professional to welcome the homosexual in the process of own and family acceptance are scarce, as there are still several constraints and other types of problems, such as the lack of preparation of professionals. Therefore, it is clear that there is a need to deepen the theme, mainly with research directed to nursing. An implementation of permanent education actions in the health of the LGBT population would help to combat prejudice, carry out campaigns in order to show the population sexual diversity together with the permanent training of professionals.

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EDUCATION , SOCIETY AND PSYCHOANALYSIS : POSSIBILITIES FOR A RELATIONSHIP CRITIQUE

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ABSTRACT : The objective of this search is to search _ relationship between psychoanalysis and education , possible elements what exceed The psychologization From problems educational essentially in origin Social, policy and economic . However , one cannot rule out the aspect fruitful of this relationship , which can be the use of hermeneutics psychoanalytic allied to criticism culture dialectic . _ To us we appropriate a reading frankfurtiana of Freud 's thought , we seek Show The importance of psychoanalysis for reflection on the production of knowledge , on the teacher - student relationship and for the denunciation of attitudes pedagogical merely adaptive and no emancipatory . if The ambiguity of cultural formation , and, in sense strict , education , no can be eliminated simply with a scale - receipt terminological , It is assignment gives Theory critique oppose you concepts to reality .

Therefore , cultural formation is the denial of what we experience up until then : semiformation socialized (Halbbildung) possible in to be seized at education per through parameters _ pedagogical that not has in-depth your reflection about The culture and The theory of knowledge , about The democratization of teaching , The cultural industry and the Law Suit unconscious existing at relationship school - society . We claim the effort theoretical in contraposition to practicality reigning in the interventions made in for the sake of education .

Key words: Homosexuality. Relations family . Tolerance .

INTRODUCTION

In face gives concord totalitarian what touts immediately as sense The elimination of the difference , it is possible that temporarily , until even something of the social force of liberation behold withdrawn to the individual sphere , and in Brazil , psychoanalysis he was welcome us speeches pedagogical as form in solve O problem in “ children maladjusted ”, “ abnormalized fur quite Social”. So , in relationship at children labels of up until then of “ abnormal ”, defending , in the field of mental hygiene , the insertion of theory psychoanalytic . Abstaining from the analysis of institutions , task attributed to sociology , mental hygiene aimed diagnose , prevent and correct personality and conduct problems , the cause of which would be at influence power of misfit means , conflicts households , malnutrition , labor exploitation , drugs . _ For Arthur Ramos, no there would be only the “ child problem “, but substantially “ child problems “ socially determined not to demanded - laugh one criticism of society as a whole , rather a “ correction ” of the family environment by through adult analysis . __ Although Arthur Ramos detect the cause of maladjustment , essentially , as action of the environment , in a perspective eugenics , had as assignment fundamental “ transform you impulses that go against the environment in impulses Useful to middle .

DEVELOPMENT

Despite the advance in the ideas pedagogical Brazilians , to the criticize theories _ racists and geneticists who predominated at explanation of failure school, he was maintained The tradition in “ no if speak gives force in the house of the hanged man ”, or that is , never attributing “ maladjustment “ to the division of class society . However , it is possible think one contributed psychoanalysis to education in moldsno conservatives?The psychoanalytic knowledge can something do to individual who, having explicit your unconscious , you have to return to a partnership __ regulated by the objectification of the conscious ? Obviously psychoanalysis lends itself to the critique of knowledge and society , but not stop being her same social product .

individual and society they can dispose of psychoanalysis as instrument of clarification , but the desire not to know can be relegated to second plan .

No they are us horizons of this job to recover one likely education psychological , whose attempts , disconnected from a society criticism , _ has been so little profitable at the sense in improve The health mental _ From individuals , much any less suggest one transposition , without more , gives clinic “.. for some little room encrusted in the corner hidden from a school ” which would be , at the very least , obscurantism .

THE school by _ your ambivalence , deserved from Adorno a certain look and listen psychoanalytic in order to clarify in it the tension between culture and barbarism . To space circumscribed to the school , it is suggested to formation and conscience psychoanalytic tools for teachers , parents and students . However , this clarification no aims properly ends pedagogical , but anti -pedagogical . Assuming the procedure common to Critical Theory , the negation determined that understands knowledge _ as complaint of illusion , it is deposited in the school the few possibilities to do in front of barbarism civilized . if at school effort is allied to psychoanalysis – _ per example , the inherent taboos to the teachers being thought and resolved at own formation professional in instead of being your base , not would you like say we have found the solution unique and definitive however , “...a clarification a little enough and just partially efficient it ‘s still better than none ”

This illustration via listening psychoanalytic and self- reflection criticism - in a word , thought – and experience , from which the de - barbarization be possible , have in their favor the action anti- pedagogical aspect of psychoanalysis that does not he must go to meeting of improvement , but of the disarticulation of the school as we know it , experience it and perpetuate it . the doctrines pedagogical are essentially egoic , to the seek control and predictability of development _ child ‘s cognitive and emotional _ _ to take in account The impossibility structural of that domain . an education analytics

only would be possible at the moment in which the education resign to your own foundation . It is therefore necessary to make a differentiation between education and discourse about education , pedagogy . The knowledge of the impossibility of controlling the unconscious doesn't just lead to a position ethic extremely valuable . take us to power think one education no totalitarian and emancipatory .

O rigor with what you dominators prevented at the course From centuries to your own descendants , well like the masses dominated , relapse in ways of life mimetics – starting with the prohibition of images in the religion , passing through the social proscription of actors and gypsies and finally arriving at a pedagogy that wean children from being _ children - is the very condition gives civilization . THE education Social and individual reinforces us men your behavior objectively While workers and prevents them from getting lost in the fluctuations of nature environment . All fun , all abandonment it has something of mimicry . It was by stiffening against it that the ego was forged . It is through in your constitution that the passage takes place gives mimesis reflector for reflection controlled .

What is fundamental is not the reappropriation of the mimetic as magic and regression : mimesis would indicate much most one dimension essential of thinking , That dimension in approximation no violent , playful _ One approach of other what get understand it without arrest him and oppress him, knowledge without violence nor domination . That knowledge only would be possible with the recognition of strange , as defined Freud: O secretly familiar that was subject The repression , but returned , anyway , O what it should to have remained hidden but came to light.

That weird would be everything it says respect for nature no totally conformed fur process civilization , which refers to mimesis original , dispossessing the subject of himself same , as the corporeality , the experience aesthetics , O suffering . O welcome and conviction with you conflicts and joys of otherness no they are us limits of a therapy , since this other one is socially

located in the “ misfits ”, “ abnormal ”, “ weak ” who do not match with you taxes in productivity , efficiency and obedience . if “ everything that did n't fit fully or that hurts you prohibited in which secular progress has settled has an effect irritating and provokes one repug - nancy compulsive ” the ethics of compassion require not only self - knowledge via enlightenment psychoanalytic , but a transformation Social: production mode bourgeois , the indelible heritage mimetic of all praxis is abandoned to oblivion . You men obsessed with civilization only if realize in their own strokes mimetics , what if became taboo in certain gestures and behaviors that find in others and that stand out in your world rationalized as waste isolates and traces rudimentary truly shameful _

Therefore , the criticism at production relations and knowledge _ so due allow overcome theories _ explanations of failure , of maladjustment , which seek level and empty the contradictions of the process civilization , locating them in the biological and/ or silencing the determinations social .if the construction civilizing it is founded at denial of the unconscious , of the capacity mimicry , so that one can claim you powers of conscience , reason , exploitation of work , the greatest contribution that psychoanalysis __he can to give to education is, precisely , to show its impossibility . It is necessary leave you exaggerations aside to seek a balance point _ _ in which the educator can benefit from psychoanalytic knowledge . In psychoanalysis nothing is true but your _ exaggerations . At this point , maybe be need Search for not the point of equilibrium , but the point of disequilibrium , where the conflict space _ can be explained and what was _ mute -do can be heard . A pedagogy that takes the phenomenon of consciousness seriously _ contradictory no would be interventionist , dirigiste , totalitarian , would rather work for the resistance . But this amounts to pedagogy think your _ historicity , to look into yes same , to make possible The education emancipatory .

Suppose a teacher having worked on Freud 's ideas and in Marx if decide for the criticism of humanism bourgeois _

THE leave of that moment , the education would be a problem for him and not one solution , because what there is to form another one when the strength is known irreducibility of the unconscious and the dissimulation systematic of exploitation through the morality of responsibility ? For such a teacher, form no would be inform to the students about of those questions and discuss them with they ? But as could that teacher has the intention of training for “ freedom ” knowing the role corrosive and repressive of culture as superego and the meaning of a society that reproduces itself by replacing repression (of body and spirit) through exploitation economic ? No would this teacher be playing precisely us limits and in illusions of humanism ?

It is hypothesis only can be lifted , let's see well , in a perspective in which you glimpse no only psychoanalysis , but the thought of Marx. This data is essential in this situation hypothetical cited per Chauí . IT IS one certain reading Marxist in Freud what he can become fruitful The relationship between psychoanalysis and education . In the following Adorno's considerations , we observe a positioning critical before the “ limits and illusions of humanism ” , from a reading of Freud and Marx:...the knowledge psychological defended as theory precisely by Freud (...) is found in agreement also with the possibility of sublimating in such a way the called aggression instincts , about which even he _ _ manifested conceptions quite many different during your life , so precisely _ they lead to trends productive . Therefore , I believe that in fight against barbarism or in your elimination there is a moment of revolt that could he own be designated as barbaric , if we started from a concept formal of humanity . But since everyone _ we us we find in the context of own guilt _ system , nobody will be entirely free from traces of barbarism , and all will depend on guiding Those strokes against principle of barbarism , in instead of allowing your course in towards the disgrace .

The watchword is , therefore , the defense condition immediate from survival of humanity , historically threatened , not a concept ahistorical of humanity . Psychoanalysis is not enough for that ,

because the structure dynamics of the psyche presented by Freud – the relationships between O Id, Ego and Superego – already no are enough in capitalism monopolist :

psychoanalysis _ introduced the little internal company that was thus constituted _ as one dynamics complicated of the unconscious and the conscious, of the id , ego and superego. In the conflict with the superego , the control instance _ Social at the individual , O ego keeps at pulses inside From Limits gives self -preservation ... But in the era of the great corporations and wars world , the mediation of the social process by countless monads appears retrograde . _ You subjects of the economy instinctual are expropriated psychologically and this economy It is managed most rationally for the own society . THE decision what O individual he must to take in each situation no need most result from a painful internal dialectic of moral conscience , self -preservation and drives . for the people at ball professional , decisions are taken by the hierarchy that goes from the associations up until The management national ; at ball private , fur scheme gives culture in mass , what expropriates their consumers forced from their last impulses internal . Associations and celebrities _ assume at functions of ego and of Super ego, and at pasta , stripped down up until even the appearance of the personality , they allow themselves to be modeled much most docilely , according you models and words in order given, of what you instincts for the internal censorship . If, in liberalism , the individuation of a part of the population was condition of adaptation of society _ _ in your all to stage of the technique , today , the operation of the apparatus economic require one direction of the masses who do not be disturbed by individuation ... The irrationality of adaptation docile and applied to reality becomes , for the individual , more rational than the reason .

Thus , the “ work of culture ”, object of psychoanalysis , expresses at sentence “ where there was the Id, let there be the Ego”, does not consubstantiate due to siege of subjectivity and the encapsulation almost unconscious automatic . _ so much so that already it 's not possible speak without “ sublimation ” caveats From instincts ” for

the which The civilization it would have if engendered up until so but from your domestication to increase productivity and consumption . _ the creativity and The fruition for the art they are reduced The release and to immediate training of the unconscious via technicism and cultural industry . the result of this no it can be culture why has per principle and purpose The indifferntiation . You individuals of beings social conform , then , to the category of beings socialized what is your own denial . we live in one situation in which for many – in understanding since it’s already a shame say “I”. Hence the need for a criticism that thinks about the “ thingification of souls”: “ Technology is the owner of no only yours _ bodies , but also of their spirits ...”. The task of psychoanalysis , in this sense , would be to denounce the socialization progressive , result gives weakening of ego in the current conditions of material survival that perpetuate the barbarism : like today in day is extremely limited possibility to change the assumption objectives , that is, the social and political ones that generate such events , the attempts to oppose repetition of Auschwitz are impelled necessarily to the side subjective .

No there may be cultural criticism without critique of relationships in work and production , because culture is constituted at materiality and on historicity . But reflect about Is it over there presupposes a to look what surpass O unveiling of the class struggle that it would be hiding . Without that horizon We do only what Adorno calls “ cultural criticism ” summoned and closely hitched The a concept uncritical gives culture , in what O critical cultural think to have concluded your task , to to do The correspondence in between O object The to be criticized and you interests in classes what he reflects , The criticism immanent continue looking for real content _ implicit at falsehood. THE psychoanalysis, in this sense , It is a time privileged dacritic immanent , then Freud analyzed with seriousness O contents in truth of formations psychic . Adorno explains well what he understands by criticism immanent / dialectic of culture , in general lines , to consider that it is posture before the object is that of not hypostasis you standards

cultural nor that of if restrict The terms operational , The The end in to do justice The she , O what no means a involvement complete at the object and, yea, transcend gives conscience , as categories of understanding , beyond immanence . _ “only it will be able to follow the dynamics object ‘s own who in him no you are completely developed ”. That double movement in direction to object (involvement and not involvement) is a subsidiary of Freud ‘s critique of culture , of consider that it is done for and against the interests of the individual . Also important to consider _ _ _ The impossible - of we be completely and totally oblivious to mechanisms ideological . the educator needs to be a critic of culture , more than a citizen sincerely concerned about citizenship . critique immanent and dialectic of culture and self- reflection criticism are assumption fruitful of a relationship between psychoanalysis and education that has as point of departure and arrival to transformation of conditions objective . Psychoanalysis , therefore , is not incompatible with _ _ education , but with the doctrines pedagogical , to the enable at least one redirect _ _ at formation of teacher.

If the findings Freudians , such as the unconscious and hermeneutics psychoanalytic , no match the promises of the culture , they can be critical references of knowledge and education , through which this knowledge has been legitimized . THE school , emerging as answer to birth of the state, of the family , of property deprivation and the social division of labor , the malaise at education is a result of malaise at civilization . To withdraw from confrontation as horror is to allow it to perpetuate itself . the ignorance in the face of suffering provoked by the mechanisms of domination is it own . In others words : ... education need take seriously what already _ deha much is known to philosophy : queo fear no he must to be repressed . When O fear no It is repressed , When us allow - mos to have really so scared how much this reality demands , then precisely per That via will disappear probably great part From effects deleterious of fear unconscious and repressed .

It is no wonder that the educational process you have failed. To mute, hide, or simply not know your taboos and your side obscure, the school community – and, in last instance, civilization sees herself imprisoned per This one hidden which is manifested by example, in what he calls “double hierarchy”, observable at school, in which pedagogical research it should pay special attention: “...the hierarchy official, according to intellect, performance, grades, and hierarchy unofficial, in which the force physics, “being a man” and a whole set of skills practical physical no honored by the hierarchy official play a paper”.

“To be man” put yourself in opposition to effort intellectual. In this duo hierarchy, in which the division between labor is expressed physical and work intellectual, there also the problem of competition – grades, selected classes (the well-known “A” classes), whose strengthening is contrary The one education human. In that case, there is one apparent appreciation from work intellectual because, after all, if the important thing is to be the strongest – no matter if physics or mentally – the cultural formation is already abolished why undifferentiated with your otherwise, to the analyze those who have answer to everything, consider that: “the intelligent people have always made things easier for barbarians, because are stupid”. If the school intends humanize the individual, it is necessary to focus on the inhuman in the human.

It is necessary assume the wound narcissistic provoked by the discovery of the unconscious, recognizing that barbarism implied at culture no he must be at the service of a teacher weakening. Knowledge is not imposed, but it is not he can dismiss The authority. The human being autonomous and therefore emancipated – no constitutes simply protest against any type in authority, to which you see O time gives authority as assumption of emancipation. But glorification and conservation of this time constitutive of individuality leads to the sense contrary to desirable, or that is, to minority in the sense Kantian: the inability to make use of one’s own understanding. People become – emancipated The leave

gives identification with authority, with later frustration with it and its overcoming. However, it occurs quite often The identification with the aggressor.

The adaptation process, which takes place in a painful way, passes, necessarily, by an exaggerated realism in relation to you even. Adorno understands that the criticism This one realism overvalued, the stuff of identification with the aggressor, needs to be evaluated, above all, in the first childhood.

To analyze The ambivalence gives relationship teacher – student and society – teacher is wanted rare to understand The aversion to teaching that is not limited to only at considerations about being a poorly paid profession. There is in this aversion Law Suit unconscious that already no are based on facts goals, but give account of motivations subjective little discussed and by that same worrisome. Being a teacher implies to charge The scribe image of monk – disempowered – storms, from someone holder of little knowledge – efficient in a world where, implicitly, the force physical determines considerable part of life Social.

This implies that, despite the abolition of punishments physicists at school and the so propa-sides children’s rights, there are The Image teacher’s unconscious as torturer, jailer, executioner, of one who has power about beings fragile per your range age or per your ignorance. Towards The scarcity structural of our schools, the teacher does not it achieves go much in addition to a keeper children. Of any way, inequality inherent in the relationship pedagogical put the teacher in situation suspicion and eternal vigilance, making him, at the same time, same time, an eternal watched in your reactions, in your preferences affective – which, incidentally, is not he must express, under penalty of being considered unfair. From a castrator, the teacher becomes a neutered:

On the one hand, he no has occupation erotica; on the other hand, it plays a big role paper erotic for teenagers dazzled by example. But in most cases – only as object

unattainable ; just observe in him traces of sympathy , to defame him as unfair .

This exclusion almost always just formal of the sphere erotic , concealed most of the time in sublimation – the teacher has to be an example of discretion and self -control as herald of civilization , is reflected at conscience mutilated that not tolerates the free expression of the body . The disposition of the portfolios , the “keep quiet ” order are more than postures disciplinary - is the immobilization physical expressing the enclosure of the spirit . THE indifference with The own pain and The pain of other It is The brand of this education for the discipline through O rigor, Image veil of sadism and of masochism , so expensive to fascism. the relationships objects at school deserved one special attention from Adorno. Precisely per no be discussed , become taboos , prohibiting the distinction between work and _ purpose and affection staff . A fully-fledged teacher goal , or be professional _ strictly , would appear inhuman and cold , but give flow rate yours effectiveness without being able to have control about that is to submit to representations that are made his . Being that the teachers no should repress their affections for later leave them sprout rationalized , without recognize them _ towards yes and the too much :

Probably a teacher what says : “yea, I am unfair , I l’m one person as you , to whom something pleases and something displeases ” will be most convincing than another supported ideologically - logically at justice , but that ends inevitably _ _ committing injustices repressed .

This us refers to the issue of school evaluation and the implications that the behavior student ‘s disciplinary has about she . How can the teacher effectively evaluate the student more _ humane and just , if it is not possible for he gives himself account of the contradictions inherent he own ? It seems to us that it is not just ethics _ professional , but to put yourself at the table of discussions pedagogical as much as subjective has a teacher - student relationship and not simply put the teacher in neutral position to evaluate _ some thing . In the case of failure , one is at the mercy , and

this is the expression of the democratization of education - of vehement appeals verbal and formal (features in instances superior to the school), enough for them to be valid only any mistake or forgetfulness of the teacher or the collective of teachers in the evaluation process . Although you speeches no be so explicit , the teacher is effectively not considered able to assess your _ work and its impact on students . Uncertainty , weakness , falsehood and injustice are concepts that involve teaching , without this _ _ can be said clearly and recognized .

THE requirement of objectivity for the teacher who must contain , repress everything that is subjective at your relationship with the students also it is related to the maintenance of society that fears the different and the potential transformer contained in the particular. an understanding criticism of what if intends with it is objectivity and O what there is in so fearsome at subjectivity the teacher-student relationship perhaps could bring to the ours horizons some humanization perspective . _ the subject he can save in if a power objective still greater than categorizations comprehensive and pre-established – the so - called criteria of scientificity in positivism or the concept of style in the arts , by example . in the world totally managed , the process persecutory against _ objectivity of the subject (understood as subjectivity in a sense of immorality and incompetence to discern) is used to leave you in eternal impotence . Thus , objectivity , which has per The end unmask postures ideological , yes, she same instrument _ ideological to treat everyone _ as things .

CONCLUSION

Addressing subjectivity critically allows analyze and transform the conditions objective no only of the individual , but of the society that the besiege . At explanations psychological are partial , but necessary , The measure that can unmask the forces irrational , which, in name of reason , dominate coercively the individual .

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The school he comes suffering consequences through the modifications in function of your action transformer to over the years. Today therefore insert all your _ acting in the context critical to meet the evolution of modernity and play a role no conservative most dynamic , follow O time transformer globalized so the psychoanalysis it is

contained and expands the action of speaking and listening in the sense most broad to unmask the forces irrational , which, in name of reason , dominate coercively the individual .

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ANALYSIS OF SUBSEA EQUIPMENT IN DEEP WATER AND ITS ECONOMIC VARIATION

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INTRODUCTION

The process of selecting project alternatives for oil field developments in deep waters is an important step in ensuring the success of the fluid extraction and processing enterprise. As each reservoir has different characteristics and properties, develop a preliminary and objective assessment of the options for the relevant project. The number of wells, their positioning, length, diameter of production pipelines, wet or dry Christmas trees, subsea equipment associated with the Stationary Production Unit (UEP) including technological analysis and system flexibility, to maximize the chances of selecting the development arrangement most suited to the characteristics of the reservoir.

The subsea production system to which this study refers is about the layout in which the interconnection lines, positioning of the Christmas tree, control and injection system that will be on the sea floor are designed. During this process, alternatives will be generated, that is, indications of use or not of equipment, types of platforms, submerged pumping systems, among others.

Thus, the present study aims to understand the construction and installation of arrangements for extraction and lifting

of petroleum fluids considering the subsea system in deep waters and to develop the possible conceptual configurations of the production system for an oilfield project. The purpose is to meet the maximization of oil recovery with a basic cost assessment in general that includes CAPEX (capital investment) and OPEX (operating cost) analysis.

METHODOLOGY

The present study will be of the case study type with research of the comparative type where will be studied all at alternatives viable for use of the subsea production arrangement.

O development in a project in system in production offshore , involves a body multidisciplinary, each stage require a level in knowledge advanced at the what it says respect to the materials and services addressed, being then in Dice real obtained in form in Query at companies of this branch. O gift field petroleum demand one solution for enable The exploration and production in Petroleum at the sea considered currently viable and a new method for your Implementation. Most specifically if refers The one settings From equipment submarines proposal for four wells in Petroleum and is based at evaluation gives rate in variation in CAPEX (

capital expenditure) and OPEX (operational expenditure)

RESULTS

1. Description of Field in manu

Ofield in manu It is a field fictitious although adequate The reality. IT IS an offshore reservoir , located 100 km off the coast of Rio de Janeiro with volumes recoverable in between 15 The 20 thousand barrels in Petroleum per day (bpd) in each well, oil that is of good quality with 33°API, that is, relatively light, as it is basically constituted by alkanes and a percentage of 15 to 25% in cycloalkanes, in addition in gas Natural associated. That field it has four wells The one blade water in 1,000 meters, O project It is estimated for 15 years of production and the price per barrel used in the calculations must be US\$ 111.25 as reported by Jornal Nicomex Notícias in November 2012

Any pit in Petroleum The to be perforated he must to satisfy The some parameters minimums, then for the project to be economically viable, the cost with the implementation From several equipment necessary for the exploitation of the deposit it has to be advantageous. As a main parameter, for the economic evaluation of the project, the estimation of the volume of the deposit stands out. O field producing in your capacity maximum he can to arrive up until 80 thousand bpd.

2. Data From Equipment submarines

The construction of Table 2 was carried out based on the data and values for the period of September 2012 at the Rio Oil & Gas event – Rio de Janeiro January - Brazil and through in interviews with professionals of sector. For continuation of that study he was researched O cost in each equipment submarine justifying and evaluating the rate of change of your CAPEX and OPEX to the data in the table consist of estimates, analyzes with the professionals interviewed.

TYPE IN EQUIPMENT SUBSEA	OCCUPATION	SPECIFICATION	COST
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Tree in Christmas Wet	Allow the well control in production or injection.	IT IS constituted per a block wrought, where they are mounted at valves in manual lock and hydraulics;	CAPEX \$ 800,000.00 OPEX \$ 200,000.00 Total \$ 1,000,000.00
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Flowline	Carry oil and/or gas from wells to the manifolds , carry oil and/or gas from manifolds up until The platform, carry Water and other substan- ces of platfor- ms of produc- tion, through manifolds _ in injection, up until The head in pit in injec- tion.	IT IS The pipe in head return from the well, through the which The mud raisin for The sieve oscillating. He can to be also the pipe per Where pass the oil or gas produced.	CAPEX \$ 6,000,000.00 /km OPEX \$ 6,000,000.00
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FPSO	It is used for exploita- tion, storage and flow gives production for ships tank.	Platform with Format in ship, it has 6 mouths for riser and has maximum ca- pacity for 200 thousand bpd.	\$420,000,000.00 The unity or Rent: \$ 150,000.00/ day and OPEX \$ 26,000.00
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Manifold Subma- rine	Get together in form balanced and controlled production in several wells in only one only pipe in production.	IT IS constitu- ted per piping arrangement, set of valves block, valves in control in drainage and subsystems monitoring, control and interconnection. arrangement, set of valves block, valves in control in drainage and subsystems monitoring, control and interconnec- tion.	CAPEX \$ 8,000,000.00 OPEX \$ 2,000,000.00 Total \$ 10,000,000.00
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Ship reliever	Used for transport of Hydrocar- bons.	Ships in two hooves, a It is O own hull of ship and the other is the wall of tank in Petroleum.	\$ 350,000.00/ day
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Table two: Cost in Each Component of System

Source: Search FMC Technologies, Technip – interview 2012 and Magazine Petroleum and Energy - 2011

The petroleum engineer often uses specific software to simulate at interrelationships in between you equipment submarines and to evaluate at best possibilities for if to take one decision. These tools make possible characterize and simulate O process in production in a reservoir The leave in information relative to the Dice of place, representing O positioning of the wells and simulating the flow of fluids in this reservoir virtual, aiming get information what make possible optimize The production.

Alternatives in Project

At alternatives The be evaluated were analyzed and developed calculations mathematicians for to determine at possible options in arrangements productive through of which The production can to be carried out in form economic.

The implementation of the subsea arrangement type in the Manu field will be elaborate from a comparison between the four alternatives offered. The specification of the best system for the project will be based on the rate in variation in CAPEX and OPEX calculated.

Such challenges take The need in development in new methods what allow design, with The minimization in scratches and costs O best scenery at the processing in oil and gas.

Alternative THE

For The first alternative use one platform type FPSO connecting the four wells, two flexible risers of 660 meters each, two PLETS, a manifold for junction of lines of production. For the PLEM and The Christmas tree uses up four outfits each. As for the flowline are four ducts also, being what each a give me 495 meters. At valves in block will be operated per a remotely Operated vehicle (ROV).

In Figure 12, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative a.

Figure 12: Flowchart of Alternative A

Source: Built by author

Analysis economic gives Alternative THE

Expected to recover fence in 60 thousand bpd, with O plan in proposed development and peak production will be reached in 2014, at 80 thousand bpd.

This analysis will be based on the purchase of an FPSO for 15 years of operation with storage capacity of 900 thousand barrels of oil, being so O ship reliever only will make O offloading two times per month, justifying O rent diary for The operation. O ROV it will be bought.

THE Table 3, show The specification of CAPEX already with O number in equipment calculated and O time of project estimated.

Table 3: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative THE

Description	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	4 in 495 meters	US\$ 11,880,000.00
FPSO	1	US\$ 420,000,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times per month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
PLEM	4	US\$ 14,400,000.00
PLET	two	US\$ 1,300,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: built by author

O investment It is referent The need in disbursement for The acquisition of the item and the operating cost is related to the operating and maintenance. O value in OPEX considered at Table 4, express O cost operational Yearly for O system in study.

Table 4: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative THE

Description	capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christma	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 360,000,000.00
FPSO	US\$ 390,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 24,000,000.00
PLET	US\$ 4,500,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: built by author

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative THE, according shown at Table 5.

Table 5: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative THE

Total CAPEX	US\$ 593,960,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 565,740,000.00
Total General	US\$ 1,159,700,000.00

Source: built fur author

At analysis in cost note what O investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 593.96 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 565.74 millions at the Final in all O project.

In one year of production, the field will produce 21,900 barrels of oil soon, O project It is economically viable, then O barrel it will be sold The US\$ 111.25 thousand totalizing US\$ 67.58 billion.

Alternative B

At Monday alternative use also one platform of type FPSO to receive the production of the four oil wells and two risers of 660 meters each, which in turn is connected to a manifold. O use of a PLEM in

that model it will be for to receive you ducts in Petroleum From four different wells and connect to other production pipelines that will be connected directly to manifold, of this form there is one reduction in amount in investments and also the costs to be spent on the project. use four Christmas trees and the help of an ROV. It is important to note that two flowlines measure 330 meters and you others two measure 220 meters.

In Figure 13, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative B.

Figure 13: Flowchart of Alternative B
Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative B

Inside in three months, you four wells producers in Petroleum will be interconnected to the FPSO, in order to gradually increase the production of the field. In wake up with calculations mathematicians, The FPSO go to introduce one production in 60 thousand barrels in oil equivalent per day at the first quarter, soon after your production increase for 80 thousand bpd for what so be reached the purpose of project.

In this stage will be performed at activities in calculation and analysis in sensitivity

of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative B, The analysis economic will be made based on the specification of the equipment and implementation of the same, taking into account the purchase of an FPSO and an ROV. The ship reliever it will be rented per a period in 15 years old.

THE Table 6, show The specification of CAPEX already with O number in equipment calculated and O time of project estimated.

Table 6: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative B

Description	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	two in 330 meters	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	two in 220 meters	US\$ 2,640,000.00
FPSO	1	US\$ 420,000,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times per month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
PLEM	1	US\$ 3,600,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: built by author

It will also be taken into account that for each item presented there is a existence in information in investment and cost operational in 15 years old. O value of OPEX considered in the Table 7 expresses itself the cost operational for you equipment.

Table 7: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative B

Description	capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christma	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 360,000,000.00
FPSO	US\$ 390,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 6,000,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: built by author

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative B aiming

at comparison with data from other alternatives to be made at the elapse of this study, according shown at Table 8.

Table 8: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative B

Total CAPEX	US\$ 576,580,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 543,240,000.00
Total General	US\$ 569,980,000.00

Source: built fur author

At analysis in cost note what O investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 576.58 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 543.24 millions at the Final in all O project.

In addition from that, equal The alternative previous, O horizon in time in implantation It is in a year for recovery in all O your capital invested. This model presented an evolution of the costs spent during the project, when step what no has in two PLETS and three PLEMs becoming so O design with other viable alternative.

Alternative Ç

One turn what The depth gives Water decreases significantly to far away in 100 km gives coast, reaching 1000 meters in depth, The platform spar buoy it went out as one option.

This system has some advantages over the FPSO, such as excellent behavior in severe seas, its performance is great in blades water deep and ultra-deep, it has great capacity in storage.

In that arrangement it will be implemented in addition gives platform type spar Buoy , two risers in 660 meters each a, four trees in Christmas, three flowlines in 220 meters and one of 330 meters that will be directly connected to the manifold to join of lines of production.

In Figure 14, a planned subsea arrangement scheme is presented. for the alternative C.

Figure 14: Flowchart of Alternative Ç
Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative Ç

For this alternative, a Spar Buoy platform will be purchased . To the Underwater inspection an ROV will also be purchased. the relief ship will be rented twice a month so that offloading can be done , as the maximum storage capacity of Spar Buoy platform is 1000 barrels in Petroleum. That alternative will have a flow rate in 60 thousand bpd us its first five months and 80,000 bdp by the end of its operation. No with no production stoppage during the 15 years of operation, this platform can to produce up until 401,500 thousand barrels in Petroleum.

IT IS fundamental The individualization of specifications in each subsea equipment used in the project and its due associated costs to time in operation estimated for to guarantee transparency and safety during The life productive of field.

THE Table 9, show The specification of CAPEX for each equipment already with

The the amount you same calculated it's the time from the project estimated for 15 years.

Table 9: Specification of CAPEX for The Alternative Ç

Description	The amount	Capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	3 in 220 meters	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	1 in 330 meters	US\$ 1,980,000.00
manifold	1	US\$ 8,000,000.00
Ship reliever	Rent two times to month	US\$ 126,000,000.00
riser	two in 660 meters	US\$ 5,280,000.00
spar buoy	1	US\$ 340,000,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: Built by author

Among the financial math questions was developed the table 10, Where resume at conditions for O project consolidate your capital in operation and maintenance to far away of period in 15 years old at the field in Manual

Table 10: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for

The Alternative Ç

Description	Capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christmas	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 276,000,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
spar buoy	US\$ 318,750.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: Built by author

The process of selection of equipment for the development of a subsea arrangement in a deep water oil field is a step important ensuring O success of project.

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative C at Table 11.

Table 11: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative C

Total CAPEX	US\$ 492,320,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 453,168,750.00
Total General	US\$ 945,488,750.00

Source: built by the author

At analysis in cost note what investment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 492.32 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 453,168 millions.

Alternative C has as a return up to its fifth year of operation more in US\$ 65,213 billion being so one option in arrangement submarine economically viable.

Alternative D

Spar Buoy platform is also used. for to receive The production of four trees in Christmas what they are connected to manifold per four flowlines being a measuring 330 meters and you others measuring 220 meters. Important highlight what in this alternative in arrangement the submarine uses two PLETs that make the interconnection of the flexible duct with the rigid duct what in turn measures 660 meters, thus facilitating the use of the ROV what it will be bought. O use in four PLEMs it will be for to secure The operation of system serving for turn on O set submerged in ducts. Through in valves operated fur ROV in that equipment O set in ducts has The option in to be isolated and O pipeline closed at the case in a blowout, per example.

In Figure 15, a type of subsea arrangement is presented that can be implemented in the Manu field with its maximum flow from second year of

operation, arriving The 80 thousand bpd.

Figure 15: Flowchart of Alternative D

Source: Built fur author

Analysis economic gives Alternative D

Spar Buoy platform is used for the field production, with the advantage of flexibilizing the production capacity charge at the deck, being that O first concept of that type in unity of developed float. as the field of Manu is found 100 km away gives coast no having possibility of fluid produced for the platform to be flowed through an oil or gas pipeline, according to the flow of the system submarine O process in offloading it will be done only two times to month thus ruling out the possibility of purchasing a relief ship, Where That vessel has as activity main drain The production in Petroleum or gas of units producers offshore .

THE Table 12, show you spending in expenses in capital, or be, service debt due to the capital invested to purchase the equipment that will be necessary in the implementation from the project already specifying O CAPEX in each a with O time in service calculated for 15 years old in operation.

Table 12: Specification of CAPEX for The

Alternative D

Specification	The amount	capital invested
Tree in Christmas	4	US\$ 3,200,000.00
flowline	3	US\$ 3,960,000.00
flowline	1	US\$ 1,980,000.00
manifold	3	US\$ 8,000,000.00
PLEM	4	US\$ 14,400,000.00
PLET	two	US\$ 1,300,000.00
Ship reliever	1	US\$ 126,000,000.00
riser	two	US\$ 5,280,000.00
spar buoy	1	US\$ 340,000,000.00
ROV	1	US\$ 3,900,000.00

Source: Built by author

For to evaluate O return financial in projects it will be then required know O cycle total in life expected for The production, O price The to be practiced at sale in products, at quantities what must to be produced for each product from the initial phase of pre-operation, normal operation, increase in production, period of maximum production and decline in production, spending on expenses in CAPEX and spending with at expenses in OPEX

Table 13: Specification of OPEX in 15 years old for The Alternative D

Description	Capital for Maintenance
Tree in Christmas	US\$ 12,000,000.00
flowline	US\$ 276,000,000.00
manifold	US\$ 30,000,000.00
PLEM	US\$ 24,000,000.00
PLET	US\$ 4,500,000.00
riser	US\$ 120,000,000.00
spar buoy	US\$ 318,750.00
ROV	US\$ 14,850,000.00

Source: Built by author

Really, CAPEX and OPEX no are methodologies. O first anything is more than a British expression for expenditure and/or investment of capital thus being the sum of all investments in resources

and the purchase From equipment necessary for to maintain a environment operational in production, being O second It is O what if refers to the costs and expenses operational.

From these data, the total cost of the project for the Alternative D

Table 14: Result of CAPEX and OPEX for The Alternative D

Total CAPEX	US\$ 508,020,000.00
Total OPEX	US\$ 481,668,750.00
Total General	US\$ 989,688,750.00

Source: Built by author

AtanalysisincostnotewhatOinvestment at phase in development of the field throughout the implantation period is of the order of US\$ 508.02 million, While you costs operational totals estimated stay in US\$ 481.66 millions for all O project.

Alternative D has as a return in four years of operation more than US\$ 69.95 billion being so one option in arrangement submarine economically viable.

ANALYSIS IN RESULTS

The case analyzed is a project to develop a field of oil that has a range of four alternatives, each with a scale in production different, for O development of same. So comes up the possibility of the field being developed to operate in medium or large scale, being one assignment of engineer in Petroleum The search for the excellent production. When there is only one only alternative available to engineer, no there is a choice to be made as to the scale of production. But, having more than one option in arrangement submarine, O professional raisin The to have most flexibility, already what, becomes possible choose which best alternative

in wake up with O scenery in question. O appearance in most in one option in arrangement productive only he comes add value to project.

You values used at the study were Dice real in queries and researches in companies what act in the branch oil. However, the relationship between the FPSO and shuttle ship rental values were based on contracts real what have duration in 15 years old.

For to analyze all at alternatives, aiming to meet you main requirements to start the operation in the Manu field, an analysis will be carried out separated for each layout introduced.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative THE

One time that the value in a project is based on your capacity in generate flows in boxes futures, or be, generate dividends, at alternatives in investments can be compared only if financial events are measured in a same time and, one turn what at operations in investment or financing has features in a spacing in flows in Cashier over time.

O value of money at the time It is The reasoning gives analysis in results and It is The base for at measurements in profit for select investments.

Generally, the economic evaluation of petroleum projects is carried out by quite in mathematical calculations of Which are obtained you main indicators economic.

In the evaluation of Exploration and Production projects, it is important that the equipment selected be shown in the phase in technical decision on to the decision-making process of how the oil fields should be laid out, for that It is important what you concepts be clear and integrated with O process in management from the deposit.

For The first alternative he was introduced O cost in US\$ 1,159 millions

for The phase initial of project, that result includes The purchase and O rent in equipment submarines and in subsurface.

For this alternative, the field development plan reached the your objective, in your second year in production O field in manu will be producing 80 thousand barrels in Petroleum per day.

Through gives Figure 16, It is possible to view in manner simplified The production for O field in manu for the alternative THE.

Figure 16:
Graph of Field Production by Alternative A
Source: Built fur author

You results obtained for The evaluation of price equivalent The US\$111.25 thousand O barrel in Petroleum resulted positive, indicating what Oproject It is highly lucrative.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative B

In this section, you main parameters used for The generation From results are presented for The Alternative B.

THE reservation what it is being considered behaves, in average, O equivalent The four hundred millions in barrels in Petroleum, being able be variations of up to 50% in this value, that is, the volume of the reserve considered he can be understood in between two hundred and six hundred millions in barrels in Petroleum.

For O price of Petroleum, it is considered

The amount in cent and eleven dollars per barrel being O price current, subject The volatility in 25%.

As mentioned earlier, there are four scale options many different for O development from the project, being what in your third year of useful life, the production of the field increases from 60 thousand bdp to 80 thousand bdp reaching so The your productivity maximum as shown at Figure 17.

Figure 17:
Graph of Field Production by Alternative B
Source: Built fur author

For all O investment in maintenance and operation it was considered as being a year O time for The first use of OPEX

By the results found, it is noticed what in this analysis O values spent at phase initial of p project it will be in US\$ 569.98 millions, value that starting from the pre supposed what no go there was none fact unexpected what end taking place The stop in production.

By observing the two alternatives that expose the results found, it is verified that the value of the project of the second alternative is reduced, compared with the first alternative, there is a withdrawal of three PLEMs and two PLETs where there is evidence of some changes regarding the safe operation of the submarine system. Choosing to invest in this type of operation has become any less attractive.

still notice obtaining in a result as to the profitable part of two alternatives. THE first alternative in has maximum production of field soon at the Your first year in operation While what The Monday alternative only will reach this productivity in your room year, It's fair what there is one difference partner economic in between you two models. Important highlight what The Monday option also It is treated as being one alternative in project economically viable.

Analysis in Results for The Alternative Ç

The investment in the purchase from a Spar Buoy platform Visa add value to the project so that the top From risers stay sheltered inside of the platform cylinder protecting them from waves and currents where the It is made about you ducts generally It is larger.

For that type in platform O your system account with high grade in stability, thus becoming inherent in having its center of care above your center in gravity, with The help from lower tanks that reduce the distance between the keel and the same, creating an independence of stability with your system in anchoring. Although for that type in operation It is required one technology new in addition gives your installation to be difficulty fur size gives your super structure.

The cost of capital invested in the first phase of the project is US\$945.49 billion as calculated in item 6.5.2 with a return in 15 years of operation US\$ most in 764.03 billion, making so That alternative economically viable.

O field in manu will reach The your production maximum The leave of your fifth year in operation, as shown at Figure 18. THE your production

grow upgradually, after this rapid expansion to its peak, the extraction of oil tends to remain at 80,000 bdp until the end of the project's useful life, as the As the pressure of the deposit increases and the flow of oil inside it is facilitated for the voltage superficial From pores (CAMPBELL , 1997).

Figure 18: Graph of Field Production by Alternative C
Source: Built fur author

IT IS possible O use of that type in arrangement at the field studied if no wereits complexity regarding the installation of the Floating Unit 1000 km from the coast. The choice of the best grade of steel to be implanted in the structure, adequacy From tanks, in between others.

These Law Suit in project and consultancy shall to have what idealize concepts in installation what you can toast one installation fast and efficient within the parameters required by the different security agencies, making it like this an important disadvantage compared to a platform FPSO type.

For ends in Comparison, O model most lucrative up until O gift moment is the alternative in study, but that doesn't mean it's the best to be implanted at the field in Manual

Analysis in Result for The Alternative D

To to determine O best layout in a system submarine, you costs ever

has a paper important. THE profitability It is a From main goals of investment in a project, in way to earning capacity isin extremely important.

O cost total It is most in US\$ 508.02 millions It is how much to development of field in your phase initial what has as expense O CAPEX For maintenance and operation From equipment he was calculated annually and your cost stayed in most in US\$ 481.66 millions up until O Final giveslife useful of project. whereas the production initial will be 21,900 thousand barrels and after Oits secondyear there is an increase to 29,200 thousand barrels, a value calculated with the maximum capacity of the field, as shown in Figure 19, the project in study will give one profitability in most in US\$ 819.62 billion at the Final in 15 years old of operation.

Figure 19: Graph of Field Production by Alternative D
Source: Built fur own

Although that result no It is plywood due The installation gives platform spar buoy Where he must to be considered shipments cumulative in the transport phase of some members of the structure generating fatigue until the field in Manual

At Table 15, are presented you values in return in investment in 15years old for many different values in price of barrel, of values current The minors values, comparing with O price in a environment

economic stabilized at the international market for reduction in scratches financial of enterprise for 4 scenarios of price in Petroleum which considers the value current of Marketplace The minors values in a environment economic stable, reduction of price up until The price of barrel in US\$ 33.25.

Table 15: Values in Return in Investment for 15 years old

Years in Production	Production in Oil (bbl)	Total Production in Barrel in 145 years old	Variation of Price of Barrel (US\$)
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	112.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	80.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	50.25
15	21,900,000	328,500,000	33.25

Source: Built by author

With analysis in these information you can to notice what you two first items are the most give profitability to company due to price of barrel per to be most high, soon concludes what at latest two alternatives are not viable, prices per barrel lower than US\$ 50.25 for the use of production system.

CONCLUSION

In order to analyze the different flows in the oil reservoirs, needs graphics at the excel, Where show clearly what you results of four alternatives presented reach The your productivity maximum to throughout the life of the project. Flow guarantee is viable for all options varying only at profitability of field.

considering what us fields in

Petroleum Where The installation in infrastructure is quite expensive, the use of FPSO systems ends up being one alternative quite attractive. In one situation as it is in what O place is far from the coast and operating in deep waters, the installation of a platform spar buoy no he can to be justified due to your complex installation process thus making the possibility of using an FPSO being O type in platform ideal for O project.

THE platform FPSO has as advantage about at others platforms O fact that it doesn't have to be a purpose-built structure, one can easily be converted in a ship oil tanker, offering itself as support in case in locomotion making so a ship in transport, again reducing costs and providing one structure effective to sector offshore .

With base us results found, you can conclude what The leave In this study, some advantages and disadvantages were identified for the four development and production scenarios, where we can highlight a larger flexibility for mitigate O type in arrangement submarine of field in manuand it was found what The Alternative THE requires a larger CAPEX at the value in US\$ 593.96 millions and one larger safety at execution From works offshore.

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EDUCATION AS A TOOL FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF CRITICAL THINKING

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History of critical thinking

Etymology can, in many cases, help to understand what the words themselves should mean. When trying to understand critical thinking, as a current present in the academic environment, looking at this meaning is extremely important.

According to the online Portuguese dictionary Dicio 2022, “thought is the act of thinking, becoming aware, reflecting or meditating. Faculty of conceiving, combining and comparing ideas; intelligence”. On the other hand, if the critic, also defined by Dicio, is: “relative to criticism, which is based on criteria, which establishes a value judgment for artistic, scientific, etc.”

In this way, it can be understood that critical thinking, unlike what can be assumed at another time, that it could be linked to the depreciation of something or someone, is related to the reflection on the value and contribution that a positioning, vision or idea can bring. Critical thinking is actually a tool to encourage learning and change the state of knowledge. See what he says in his article Training in Critical Thinking for Science Teachers: impact on classroom practices and students’ level of critical

thinking, CELINA TENREIRO-VIEIRA, 2004:

The results obtained support the conclusion that: teachers’ training in critical thinking influences teaching practices in relation to the teaching of critical thinking; and different critical thinking training programs influence teaching practices in critical thinking differently. Teachers who received training in critical thinking changed their practices regarding critical thinking, which became significantly “more” conducive to critical thinking.

In this way, with the globalization of information occurring instantly all over the world, it becomes increasingly necessary to analyze and investigate everything that has access, not only to investigate the veracity, but also to exercise the correct deepening of knowledge.

The Eleva platform, in an article published on its website on September 8, 2020, defines Critical Thinking as follows: “Critical thinking is the ability to analyze topics with clarity and

rationality, understanding information in an objective way and with ample capacity for judgment . Applied in the school environment and in life as a whole, it is something that involves the analysis of resources, phenomena, facts, dates and other references to assist in strategic decision making.”

When considering the importance of Critical Thinking in the school environment, several countries have already adapted their curriculum and effectively started the approach with their faculty, which in the medium term tends to raise the level of knowledge of teachers and students around the world.

Also according to Plataforma Eleva (2020) “Critical thinking is a habit. It is something that must be developed continuously, with the help of educators and family members. It is interconnected with analytical capacity, which also highlights the need for emotions are put on the back burner.” Considering then that the learning process accelerates when the student is encouraged to step out of their comfort zone and separate personal opinions from facts, through research and fundamentals.

Preparing faculty for teaching the practice of critical thinking actually brings significant changes to the promotion of critical thinking. Such practices, to which these teachers were submitted, including aspects of knowledge acquisition, appropriate methodology for the construction of curricular materials, or even, playful activities that promote critical thinking, promoting training in critical thinking on the part of these teachers, were significantly higher in in relation to teachers who were trained with a focus only on developing their critical thinking skills, according to Celina, 2004.

Preparing faculty for teaching the

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It is possible to observe in society, a portion that is not concerned with the veracity of the information they receive, the news they read, the scientific studies that guide academic life and especially the formation of elementary and high school. It is a youth disconnected from basic and fundamental values in life in society.

The questioning in search of knowledge, very present in philosophy, is somehow abandoned by this post-modern generation, which needs to receive information on a “kissed hand”. In his article Why you don’t like philosophy and maybe it’s not your fault; the author, Felipe Diego, 2018 says :

The best way to explain the path that leads someone to become an idealist or a pragmatist can be summarized in three points: (1) the lack of motivation when studying Philosophy or the absence of the correct motivation. (2) the complexity of the content itself and its time of presentation, or (3) the eventual ‘scare-off’ of the subject. It is essential to understand that, in any well-developed theory, each point implies the other [5] , so perhaps the redundancy of parts

of this text is a sign that I am speaking the truth.

Felipe lists three main points of the lack of interest in philosophy, in philosophizing, in the search for knowledge in a way that knowledge is loved, as well as describing the etymology of the word philosophy. Of these, the first may be the most intriguing, because motivation, which is what motivates us to act, which makes us leave our comfort zone, of inertia, is also the most subjective of them, as each individual can bring itself, different motivations for each action it performs.

This also highlights the importance of motivating students to this search for philosophical thinking. Encouraging this search for knowledge, questioning in a correct, scientific way, questioning not only to leave the interlocutor in a moment of embarrassment, but questioning in order to reach the point where the importance of that theme, subject, information and research is perceived.

The questioning here, whether understood as critical or philosophical thinking, does not come only as a refutation of ideas and thoughts, but also as a way of ratifying what is discussed, as well as its importance in contributing to academic development.

It is necessary to create an environment conducive to the evolution of this thought, the student cannot be expected to develop this skill overnight, it is necessary to take root during the stages and phases of their teaching. See what Felipe says about it:

Now the second point. Think about the process of building a house: first the foundations are built, then the walls and finally the roof. If construction started with the roof, you wouldn't build

a house, but an aberration that someone would call modern art. Like a house, human knowledge has a hierarchical structure of construction. First, start with simple things and then get to complex things. When we talk about knowledge, the path is from perception (concrete) to concepts (abstract). The further away from your perception, the more complex it is to grasp the concept [10].

In this way, it is necessary to create a basis for the construction of this philosophical thought and, consequently, of critical thinking. A student cannot be expected to arrive at university knowing how to perform complex mathematical calculations, without having had a basis for doing so during his high school education. In this way, we will now see how critical thinking is developed in the school environment.

Development of Critical Thinking in the School Environment

The school is a new place of socialization for the student and the classroom is a place of dialogue where the teacher and the student exchange knowledge, allowing everyone to have their points of view exposed, so that they can debate and understand subjects, for that, it is necessary to develop critical thinking.

The formation of critical thinking begins to happen mostly within the educational environment, where the student is faced with certain situations where he needs to have an initial observation and develop from this observation a critical judgment.

Critical thinking is a complex skill, it is not innate but developed throughout

life, within the educational environment this skill has to be stimulated, so that the student leaves school and enters universities already aware of the need for the think has, to continue improving critical thinking.

Unlike what is thought, the development of critical thinking begins in childhood, at the beginning of the child's school life, work and activities may already be being developed that stimulate thinking and thus developing the student's creativity and perception of the world.

When the student arrives in high school the LDB in its art. 35, clarifies that secondary education has as one of its purposes to promote "the improvement of the student as a human person, including ethical training and the development of intellectual autonomy and critical thinking". In order to promote critical thinking in high school, teachers can take advantage of classroom debates, as well as the many technologies that we have today, in addition to sensory, creative and theatrical activities.

It is necessary for educators to think about the materials to be worked on, in order to promote greater student interest, so that they begin to look at everything around them more critically, since critical thinking cannot be conditioned to walls. According to Rainbolt, "the commitment to critical thinking entails basing our beliefs on good arguments, which makes us happier, as opposed to basing them on bad arguments, which leaves us in the hands of chance".

Currently, the load of information dispensed on individuals within society and that need to be processed and understood by them, so that they can take a position in front of this sea of

information, and thus be able to look at the world critically enough to have a positioning and absorb the best.

It is necessary to understand the importance of works aimed at the formation of critical thinking, Tenreiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000), are emphatic in defending the concern of promoting critical thinking, for these:

The explanation of the growing importance and need for teaching critical thinking lies above all in the fact that critical thinking is a cornerstone in the formation of individuals capable of facing and dealing with the continuous change of the increasingly complex systems that characterize the current world (TENREIRO-VIEIRA and VIEIRA, 2000, p. 14) Therefore, the development of critical thinking in societies is notorious and emerging, as stated by Tenreiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000).

Therefore, it is understood the responsibility that the school has to form autonomous and critical citizens for the world they are inserted in, where there is a growing demand for students who have a careful look at everyday situations, where discernment will allow you to form your own opinions based on well-founded concepts.

Critical Thinking and Student-Researcher Training

In summary, we can summarize that Critical Thinking is a cognitive skill that involves analysis, logical reasoning and clinical judgment, oriented to problem solving and outstanding in training and practice. When applied to research, it opens up the possibility of enhancing other rationalities for the engagement of the various knowledge systems,

the training and professionalization of teachers, professionals in general and the university community, strengthening content and knowledge based on sustainable values and practices, with a view to making an accurate decision and achieving effective results. (MAGALHÃES, TERNEIRO-VIEIRA, 2006)

The ongoing social transformations increasingly demand research and training concepts and strategies for scientific and technological development.

The knowledge focuses are consolidated, having as references the studies about the effects of the problem on the dialogues, often interdisciplinary, allowing a new horizon for the diagnosis of social changes, breaking with reductionism and opening space for a reality permeated by uncertainties, which allows the formulation of different approaches. (JACOBI, 2012).

However, interdisciplinarity implies a knowledge process that seeks to establish transversal cuts in the understanding and explanation of the research context, aiming at the interaction between disciplines, overcoming the scientific compartmentalization caused by excessive specialization. As a combination of several areas of knowledge, interdisciplinarity presupposes the development of interactive methodologies, configuring the scope of focus. (SCHMIDT, GOMES, JACOBI, 2019). The ongoing social transformations increasingly demand interdisciplinary concepts to guide research and policy-making and development strategies, and the effects of current economic policies on the dynamics and living conditions of societies must be recognized (FUNTOWICZ, 2000).

According to Wals, 2007, the emphasis on practices that encourage interdisciplinarity and transversality reveals the great potential that exists to leave the common place and work with themes that incite changes in behavior, social responsibility and ethics, which stimulates another look, demonstrating the importance of understanding the complexity involved in the processes and the challenge of having a more reflective and active attitude, forming more responsible, careful and engaged professionals in collaborative processes with the context of society.

In this way, what is sought as the most effective teaching methodology in science education is a proposal that aims to obtain learning, scientific concepts and topics with meaning, where argumentation and the development of critical thinking are the main objective. (GUIMARÃES, MASSONI, 2020)

The concept of argumentation, based on the triad affirmative, justification and evidence, is centered on the idea of understanding science as an argument and of teaching it under the bias of argumentation. (KUHN, 1991, 1993, 2014).

For Kuhn, in this tripartite conception, the statement contained in an argument is a theory, a point of view, an idea or an opinion that one wants to prove; justification is the reason or cause that supports the claim and connects it with the evidence, observation, fact or data that supports or supports the claim.

Research promotes ways of thinking and reasoning in a meaningful way and that is closer to the way scientists do/build science, that is, always looking to review their reasoning and highlighting the mutable, provisional and not definitive aspect both in the process of developing the scientific knowledge as

well as its teaching.

CONCLUSION

According to the authors analyzed and the results obtained, critical thinking can be understood as a term related to criticism, which is based on some criterion, which establishes a value judgment for artistic, scientific works, for example.

Critical thinking is the intellectually disciplined process of conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or actively evaluating information collected or generated by observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication. In this way, critical thinking can be understood as an instrument that is capable of boosting learning and changing knowledge in a strategic way.

Countries around the world have been promoting critical thinking through the provision of training content, continuing education for teachers on issues related to Critical Thinking.

In this context, raising the level of knowledge of teachers and, consequently, of students, as observed by Celina Terneiro-Vieira (2004), who, through her results, supports that training in critical thinking for faculty is essential for promoting and passing on knowledge about this knowledge to students through teaching practices.

It is worth mentioning that the training in Critical Thinking of teachers with a focus only on their particular capacities for the development of Critical Thinking was not effective for this transfer of knowledge to the student body to happen, because a training based on appropriate methodologies for this transfer to happen is necessary. , that is, the teacher needs to learn to pass on

this type of knowledge through specific tools and methods, not only to know what critical knowledge and theories about this theme are about.

In this way, the student body becomes able to discern and analyze in an investigative and efficient way the veracity of the information accessed in this globalized world. Furthermore, the authors agree that developing critical thinking is a particular task and should be seen as “habit building” and that it should also be based on facts rather than personal opinions and emotions.

Celina terneiro-Vieira (2004) and Felipe Diego (2018) agree that the search for knowledge must be based on facts, in a scientific way, as stimulating critical and logical thinking in students can bring positive and significant changes. In this context, each student brings with him different motivations that may or may not direct him to the search for knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary that the student body loves knowledge, as well as the search for it. In experimental practice classes, in integral education schools, for example, the search for knowledge is stimulated in order to develop the logical thinking of students, in a way that knowledge is rooted through the stages of teaching with employment. a solid theoretical basis and well-designed and executed practices.

Terneiro-Vieira and Vieira (2000), Celina terneiro-Vieira (2004) and Felipe Diego (2018) share the idea that it is necessary to train autonomous and critical students, responsible for the construction of their own knowledge, as there is a need to train students with a refined and critical look so that they can deal with the changes of the modern world.

Magalhães, Terneiro-Vieira (2006) shows that critical thinking applied to

research leads to the professionalization of teachers and the training of professionals in general, strengthening content and knowledge based on sustainable values and practices, with a view to accurate decision making and reaching effective results.

It is necessary to highlight that scientific compartmentalization, for example, in laboratory practices of natural sciences and mathematics, leads to a blockage in the construction of knowledge. On the other hand, interdisciplinarity implies a knowledge process that seeks to establish transversal cuts in the understanding and explanation of the research context. In other words, when interdisciplinarity is worked on, a greater scope of focus can be accessed. In this context, it is important to highlight the continuous search of civilizations for social development that can only be achieved through technological development and quality education (SCHMIDT, GOMES, JACOBI, 2019).

Therefore, the importance of education and its effects on current public and economic policies must be recognized, as this education is responsible for the formation of more responsible, careful professionals engaged in collaborative processes with the context of society, which leads us to technological and social development so desired (FUNTOWICZ, 2000).

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GRIEVING IN THE TIME OF COVID-19: STRATEGIES FOR COATING THE PAIN AND PSYCHIC SUFFERING OF THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT:

Covid-19 originated in China, with a high transmission capacity made a rapid emergence of the pandemic. With everyone very concerned about knowing the virus and all its procedures, mental health was the one that had the least notoriety, causing many to have deficiencies in this area. The present study aims to describe the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief, discuss the psychosocial impacts of grief from Covid-19, thus, the focus is always on mental health in relation to the grief experienced. This is an integrative literature review study, in which 09 articles were analyzed, with the predominant area in the publications being Psychology. The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of coping strategies for pain and psychological suffering of the population in the face of grief, since few manage to reach the service having to resort to alternative methods, also having a great perception that the numbers of professionals qualified for this action are extremely low. Through this study, we hope to help more health professionals pay attention to the mistakes made previously during the pandemic and encourage a change in the quality of care provided to the grieving population, not only during a pandemic, but for all moments of suffering. mourning.

Key words: Death; Mourning; Covid-19; Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 PANDEMIC At the end of 2019, a new outbreak of pneumonia spread in the world population, caused by a virus called SARS-CoV-2, (COVID-19), what is known so far is that this virus originated in China, which forced different countries to mobilize to face the consequences of contamination on health and economy. Quarantine, the main way to contain the speed of contamination by COVID-19 and lethality, adopted in several regions of the world, promoted the isolation and confinement of a large number of people and the mobilization of a significant contingent of health professionals to coping with the crisis situation. Therefore, as described by Zwielewski et al (2020), the global dimension reached by COVID-19 made the World Health Organization (WHO) recognize its transmission as a pandemic. In Brazil, until September 30, 2021, 21,399,546 cases of Covid19 were confirmed, of these 20,404,701 cases are described as recovered, 398,723 cases in recovery, and 596,122 confirmed deaths, thus pointing to an incidence rate of the disease of approximately 10183, 1 per 100,000 inhabitants in Brazil, which can be viewed on the interactive COVID-19 Panel, updated monthly by the Ministry of Health (BRASIL, 2021). The main characteristic of the pandemic caused by the new coronavirus is the high transmissibility of the virus and the lethality rate varies according to the age group and clinical conditions of the patient (GRINCENKOV, 2020). Symptoms usually manifest in a clinical picture that ranges from mild cases, in which some of them may not even manifest, to very severe cases of acute respiratory syndrome. Taking into account the symptoms of the disease, the absence of vaccines and the insufficient scientific knowledge about this new virus, the most effective way to combat the proliferation of COVID-19

and a collapse in the health system is still social isolation. According to Ferguson et al (2020), there is a significant number of cases that require hospitalization and intensive care unit care, since pharmacological interventions are still insufficient and need further studies. The studies by Brooks et al (2020) and Ferguson et al (2020), point out that in order to try to control this chain of transmission and the impacts of the pandemic on the health system, considering that the number of 6 ICU beds and equipment needed for the treatment do not meet all population demand, it is extremely necessary that social isolation measures be adopted. However, Schmidt et al (2020) consider that this need has had several social and economic impacts, in addition to psychological issues that take the concerns of the disease beyond the physical symptoms.

Among these concerns, the psychological suffering experienced by both the general population and the health professionals involved in this process stands out .

Grief during the Covid-19 pandemic according to Schmidt et al (2020), Grief is a natural process in the face of the loss of someone or the breaking of a bond. Several authors have studied the theme of mourning from different theoretical approaches. In the first psychological studies on mourning, Freud (1917), in "Mourning and Melancholy" discussed a proposal in relation to the psychic dynamics of the melancholic subject, considering the perspective of the implications of object loss and of non-elaborated mourning. Freud presented mourning as a reaction to the loss of the object for which one has an investment of libidinal energy, the loss of the one one loves, culminating in behaviors that express suffering, discouragement and despondency. Unlike melancholy,

in mourning, there is the loss of a real object, and in this way, for the individual who invested energy in the lost object, the world no longer has sense or meaning that justifies the continuation with enthusiasm, these questions will be re-elaborated in a symbolic level and in the conclusion the connection of libido with another love object can occur (FREUD, 1917). Covid-19 has affected the whole world and thousands of people have died as a result of this pandemic. For the family and friends of these people, the losses are irreparable and, to deal with it, they will need a lot of support and empathy. Respect for the grieving process is one of the possible forms of care for these people, since it is a process that requires a great deal of sensitivity and subtlety, as each one can develop it in their own way, in a very unique way. This uniqueness can also be perceived in the ways in which mourning is seen, depending on the historical moment and culture of each one, since. According to Noal, Passos and Freitas (2020, p.2) “each society establishes acceptable cultural codes for the establishment of funeral rituals, which range from farewell ceremonies, tributes, to different ways of treating bodies, such as burial or cremation”. It is worth mentioning that the grieving process does not only occur when someone dies, but it can also develop due to other losses, such as, for example, the end of a relationship, the end of a cycle, the loss of a job, retirement, among others. During a pandemic, it is also common for people to suffer from what is called anticipatory grief that is expressed without the person having actually lost someone (KOVÁCS, 1992). This process is provoked in the face of uncertainties and changes in the routine of the person, who now lives isolated from their loved ones and facing the fear of losing them due to the pandemic. In this essay we specifically address the mourning of death and the

implications in this process caused by the current pandemic caused by the coronavirus that has been felt by millions of people at the same time. It is worth emphasizing that one object does not replace the space of the other, there can only be a transfer of libidinal energy from one given object to another. In this way, according to the name of the work of the aforementioned author, “Luto e Melancholia”, there is a correlation between the circumstances that appear in the title of the text, pointing out that in both there would be a profound prostration, a generalized resignation of the interest of the external world. and a considerable loss of performance (FREUD, 2017).

As already discussed in this project, Mourning is something unique. Each person reacts to loss differently. Therefore, and in agreement with Brooks et al (2020) and Xiao (2020) it is extremely important not to neglect this moment. Regarding grief in the pandemic, there are numerous psychological implications that can generate gaps and more lasting consequences in dealing with the negative consequences associated with the disease and the grieving process after death. Unfortunately, the great concern with the spread of the pandemic, the greater attention focused on the ‘cure’ or ‘eradication’ of the virus, has ignored or explored less the subject of mental health, more specifically grief. This study is based on this fact, as there are a large number of people becoming mentally ill, and the loss of loved ones significantly increases the risk of becoming ill, for this reason the group decided to talk about death, suffering, grief and the psychological impacts. We couldn’t help but talk about the professionals who are on the front lines of fighting the coronavirus, and are experiencing repeated losses, both from patients,

family members and co-workers. The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the reality and planning of people around the world. The uncertainties about the disease and the world economy affect each citizen in a particular way. The known measures to combat the transmission of the virus go through individual awareness, changes in habits and a great desire to defeat the real enemy sars-cov-2. The progressive and proportional increase in positive exams, the occupation of clinical and intensive care beds reveals the worsening, until we reach the current scenario. Fatigue invades the population and the desire to return to normal life or the new normal, the ability to respect all protocols that often seem to be exaggerated, but the solution is not individual but society. With every life lost, families and friends suffer. A team of health professionals suffers the weight of defeat and when leaving the ICU or counting the days of quarantine and there they come across people crowding in party halls, bars, amusement parks and not even using the minimum measures oriented (washing hands and wearing a mask), consume the energy of a professional who is working 24 hours on duty, but we are strong and in today's reality we are warriors and never able to give up on every human being who needs our care.

A survey carried out by the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation, comparing Brazil and Spain, shows that approximately 47.3% of essential service workers had some symptoms of anxiety and depression. More than half of them — and 27.4% of all respondents — suffer from anxiety and depression at the same time. In addition, 44.3% have abused alcoholic beverages; 42.9% suffered changes in sleep habits; and 30.9% were diagnosed with or treated for mental illness in the previous year. (UNASUS, 2020), It is worth noting that the context of Infodemia , that is, the large flow of information that spreads

quickly, has contributed to generating a large rate of misinformation. In relation to the Brazilian context, Nabuco, Oliveira, Afonso (2020) point out that in addition to Infodemia , Brazil is also experiencing the pandemic in the midst of a major political-institutional crisis. There is a structural duality, the States and the Union are in direct confrontation, disputing the model of facing the crisis, in addition to information about the real danger of the virus. There are also frequent changes in the leadership of the Ministry of Health, a federal body that should coordinate actions against the pandemic. In the midst of the dispute, the uninformed and confused population will possibly have more symptoms of anxiety, and psychosomatic problems. Based on what has been exposed, this study on grief in Covid-19 times is justified, considering that it is essential to face this reality from a broader perspective, creating specific strategies that alleviate the pain and psychic suffering of individuals.

We believe that our work is important for society and academia because talking more and more about death will break the taboos that still exist. Therefore, we want to help society and nursing students with more information as we avoid talking or thinking about death. In relation to the health team, this study is important because it returns to three important points that are impacting the mental health of this group The first refers to preventing impacts, the increase in mental health impacts related to the reduction of well-being psychosocial effects caused by the health, social and economic effects that have been affecting the entire population during the pandemic, with some population groups experiencing this more acutely. The second is about protecting people with mental illness from covid-19 and its social impacts

that can increase their vulnerability. And the third, refers to providing the necessary care to health professionals and caregivers in order to protect them too and allow them to save, protect and care for others.

Due to isolation, people cannot be with the infected patient or perform farewell rituals, actions that are part of the usual grieving process.

Public health protocols that make it impossible to visit hospitals and change traditional rituals, such as wakes and burials, impact the grieving process and the mental health of the community. In this context, the possibilities are increased for the development of a complicated grief, that is: when the grieving process takes place in a more intense and lasting way than expected, for not having been able to process the situation or say goodbye in a way that allow you to have a sense of reality and concreteness. The COVID-19 pandemic brings mental health impacts, which can involve deep loss and pain. Given this scenario, it is necessary to think about alternatives for funerals, burials and farewell rituals, it is known that farewell rituals are important for the normal grieving process of individuals and the impediment to experiencing this moment can generate intense feelings of anger, horror and shock (COGO et al. 2020) The covid-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the daily lives of most of society, the psychic always affected by fear of contamination, mourning losses of loved ones, insecurity and lack of hope in the future... many things go through the mind without the certainty that something could improve beyond the lack of accessible professional strategies for everyone in grief. Based on what has been exposed, the following research questions are formulated: What has the scientific literature published on grief in times of a pandemic? What

psychosocial impacts of Covid-19 mourning on people's daily lives? What are the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief in the face of Covid-19?

Our general objective and specific objectives are:

To review the literature on grief experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic, and its impacts on the mental health of individuals.

- Discuss the psychosocial impacts of Covid-19 grief on people's daily lives.
- Identify the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief in the face of Covid-19.

METHODOLOGY

This study is characterized as a basic, exploratory, literature review type research that uses a qualitative approach.

According to Lakatos and Marconi (2010), basic research is the one that aims to generate new knowledge useful for the advancement of science without foreseen practical application. It involves universal truths and interests. And exploratory research provides greater familiarity with the problem in order to make it explicit or to create hypotheses.

Also, the qualitative approach is research that provides meaning and simplifies social life. In this approach, "the researcher aims to deepen the understanding of the phenomena he studies - actions of individuals, groups or organizations in their environment or social context," understanding them according to the conception of the subjects who experience the situation (GUERRA, 2014, p.3).

Therefore, this integrative literature review study sought to contemplate all these characteristics described.

The survey was carried out in a virtual environment at the Virtual Health Library (VHL), in databases considered of great relevance in the scientific environment: Latin American and Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences (LILACS), Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO) and Nursing Database (BDENF), Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MedLine), using the descriptors: “Mourning”, “Covid-19”, “Mental Health”, from the Health Sciences/Medical Subject Descriptors Headings (DeCS / MeSH), from the Virtual Health Library (VHL).

Only articles published in Portuguese, with full text available online, with a time frame between 2016 and 2021, were selected. In this sense, the filters used were full text, Portuguese language, article and year. Articles whose full texts were not available online for free and results without discussion on the topic in question were excluded.

Table 1 - Number of articles found from the database search - Rio de Janeiro - 2022.

Database	Crossing the words Control of Mourning and Covid-19 and Mental Health	Number of articles after full-text filter, language and year	Number of articles after reading
lilacs	12	7	02
Scielo	06	3	03
bdenf	05	two	02
MedLine	29	15	02
Total	52	22	09

Source : Authors themselves (2022).

For data collection, an instrument built by the authors was used, containing the following variables: journal, database, year, study location, authors’ profession, title, type of research and type of document.

Table 01 : Article Data Collection Instrument - Rio de Janeiro, 2022.

Title	periodical	Data base	Year
Mourning and non-violence in times of pandemic: precariousness, mental health and other ways of living	Psychol. social	MEDLINE	2020
That goodbye, I couldn't say": grief and suffering in times of COVID-19	sick _ Focus	LILACS	2020
The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health: what is the role of Primary Health Care?	Rev Bras Med Fam Community	LILACS	2020
Social and health implications that affect people bereaved by the death of family members by covid-19	Rev. sick baiana	SCIELO	2020
Effects of suppression of funeral rituals during the pandemic of COVID-19 in bereaved family members	Rev. Latin-Am. Nursing	BDENF	2020

Terminality, death and grief in the COVID-19 pandemic: emerging psychological demands and practical implications	Study psychological	MEDLINE	2020
Implications of death and mourning on the subject's mental health in the face of the pandemic	Rev. fine psych	SCIELO	2021
Experiences of grief and nursing mental health in the COVID-19 pandemic	collective health	BDEF	2021
Nurse's role in the face of grief in times of a pandemic	Electronic Magazine Health Collection	SCIELO	2021

SP	Psychology	DANZMANN, PS et al.	Research Article
RN	Nursing	Rocha, KPM et al.	Research Article
LOL	Nursing	GONÇALVES, RMV et al.	Experience Report

Source : The Authors (2022).

Finally, the analysis, evaluation, inclusion and exclusion of the works was carried out through a critical reading of the selected works to verify their authenticity, methodological quality, importance of information and representativeness. In other words, it was based on the production of the document that includes the description of the phases covered by the reviewer and the fundamental results revealed from the analysis of the articles included.

CONCLUSION

Through this study, it was possible to understand that the condition of mourning in this new pandemic scenario is a potential generator for the development of mental disorders. And that other studies are necessary, so that it is possible to know more deeply how these grieving processes are being experienced.

The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of strategies for coping with grief from qualified health professionals for such a situation, and that the psychosocial impacts had a great alert since there was no adequate monitoring for the population.

Finally, it is essential that there is a greater focus on changes in the face of the specific demands of this new scenario imposed by the pandemic. So that there is a change in the strategic and

Place	Profession of the Authors	authors	Document Type
RJ	Psychology/ Medicine	RENT; MAM; MARHY, EE	Original article
EC	Nursing/ Psychology/ Physical Education	OLIVEIRA, EN et al.	Original article
RJ	Medicine	NABUCO, G. et al.	Research Article
BA	Nursing	M A G A -LHÃES, JRF et al.	Original article
RJ	Psychology	OLIVEIRA-CARDOSO, EA, et al.	Original article
SP	Psychology	CREPALDI, MA et al.	Original article

psychosocial parts of the population, being a multidisciplinary work and also of a university character so that there is a greater knowledge about grief and death and is not seen only as a taboo.

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ESG Principles - Sustainable Finance Responsible investment and sustainability in the financial and capital markets

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CONCEPT

The acronym ESG stands as the abbreviation for “environmental, social and governance”, _ in English “environmental , social and governance ” (ESG) and relates to the set of practices that take into account environmental, social and governance factors, aiming at achieving sustainability goals.

It is now important to explain, in greater detail, the reflection of this acronym in business strategies.

Environmental (A)

The environmental issue has gained more relevance in recent years, there is no doubt that air pollution, rivers, seas, desertification and global warming are a reality and present a dilemma where companies can be part of the problem (high carbon emissions) or part of the solution.

From an environmental point of view, it is necessary to analyze how the company operates, whether it is committed to

the preservation and correct use of resources (energy consumption and energy efficiency), implementation of recycling and waste management policies and adoption of actions with a view to to minimize the environmental impacts of its operations.

“The life of companies that emit high levels of carbon in their processes will be increasingly difficult. Not only are consumers looking for companies that are more connected with environmental issues, but the costs of being a pollutant will only increase (costs, fees and taxes)”, comments Bartunek .

In this scenario, he states that aspects to be observed in companies’ environmental issues are: energy consumption, water and energy efficiency; recycling; emission of polluting gases (example: carbon emission); preservation of biodiversity; anti-disaster measures and environmental awareness.

Social (S)

Regarding social factors, what is

observed is the way in which the company manages relationships with its employees, suppliers, customers and the community. In this “S” pillar, the actions to eliminate gender pay disparities, equal opportunities, professional development (education) of employees and also the protection of local communities can be cited as examples.

Bartunek comments that “social” encompasses the company’s relationships with its employees, customers and community. The aspects to be observed in the social issues of companies are: engagement and staff turnover; intellectual development of employees; talent attraction and retention; employee health and safety; relations with customers; supplier network and impacts on the local community.

Governance (G)

Finally, in terms of governance, companies must pay attention to issues related to their leadership, their internal controls, executive compensation, audits and shareholder rights, which can be exemplified by the adoption of policies and practices (effective and assertive) anti-corruption and bribery, antitrust, as well as any action aimed at transparency and responsibility in the business carried out.

The topic refers, briefly, to how the relationships between shareholders and controllers are governed. According to Bartunek , the aspects to be observed in corporate governance issues are: alignment and shareholder rights; in executive compensation; independence, experience and remuneration of the Board of Directors; accounting practices; soundness of internal controls and processes; related party transactions; transparency and accountability; share class structure

and corruption prevention.

Obviously, the adoption of measures related to the practice of ESG will result in expenses for the companies. However, according to Francesco Rutibliani , in an article published on the Techedge website , such expenses should be seen as investments. “In fact, companies that have incorporated ESG into their strategies have reaped several benefits, including increased market confidence and shareholder value,” says Rubliani . For investors, companies’ adoption of ESG-related policies has become an indicator for analyzing a company’s performance and its role in society.

This set of best practices has been improving in the corporate world, an example of ESG practice being the creation of the Principles for Responsible Investments (PRI), developed at the initiative of the UN program for the environment (UNEP-FI) and the Global Compact of the UN to guide the market in the search for responsible development. The Principles for Responsible United Nations Investment (PRI) is an international organization that works to promote the incorporation of environmental, social and corporate governance (ESG) factors into investment decision making.

Launched in April 2006, the PRI had over 2,300 participating financial institutions as of January 2020. These institutions participate by becoming signatories to the PRI’s six key principles by regularly reporting on their progress.

Today, signatories to the United Nations Principles for Responsible Investment account for more than \$80 trillion in assets worldwide and include some of the world’s largest and most influential investors.

UNDERSTANDING THE UNITED

NATIONS PRINCIPLES FOR RESPONSIBLE INVESTMENT (PRI)

The organization's main idea is that when making an investment decision, environmental and social factors are taken into account and are shown to be preponderant in investors' choice of companies and funds. PRI supporters argue that it is financially and ethically irresponsible not to consider a company's environmental impact when evaluating its merits as an investment. As a way of guiding company behavior, the PRI presented six basic principles, with which signatory companies must agree to commit. As expressed on the organization's website, the six principles are as follows:

Principle 1: We will incorporate ESG issues into investment analysis and decision-making processes.

Principle 2: We will be active owners and incorporate ESG issues into our ownership policies and practices.

Principle 3: We will seek appropriate disclosure on ESG matters by the entities in which we invest.

Principle 4: We will promote the acceptance and implementation of the Principles in the investment industry.

Principle 5: We will work together to increase our effectiveness in implementing the Principles.

Principle 6: Each of us will report on our activities and progress in implementing the Principles.

Together, the companies that are signatories to these six principles are responsible for a total of assets under management of more than \$80 trillion.

ORIGIN

Practices related to ESG investments emerged in the 1960s, a period in which some investors began to eliminate companies from their portfolios based on environmental, social and governance criteria. In this scenario, companies that showed little environmental and social responsibility became less attractive.

Officially, ESG investments appeared on the market in January 2004, driven by the then Secretary-General of the United Nations, Kofi Annan. He sent letters to 50 directors of large companies to support the United Nations Global Compact.

Thus, the term ESG came from the publication of the report *Who Cares Wins, Connecting Financial Markets to a Changing World*, an initiative developed by the Global Compact, together with the World Bank in 2005, which aimed to raise awareness of the need to incorporate environmental, social and governance factors in capital markets, aiming to ensure more sustainable markets and better results for societies. Concurrently, the United Nations Environment Program Finance Initiative (UNEP/FI) produced the "Freshfield Report", which demonstrated the relevance of ESG issues to financial assessment.

Thus, with these two reports and with the initiative of investors from UNEP-FI and the UN Global Compact, the framework was formed for the launch of the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI)

REFLECTIONS OF THE ADOPTION OF THE SGA

For the community, there are numerous advantages of incorporating ESG criteria by companies, this represents an evolution in the management process. By directing resources to generate positive impacts from a

socio-environmental and governance perspective, an environment favorable to sustainability is created.

The adoption of ESG criteria in the main financial markets abroad is at an advanced stage, and this issue is a reality for most investors. In Brazil the subject has been debated for some time, however, the discussion is still in an embryonic stage. In January 2020, Larry Fink, president of BlackRock (one of the largest investment fund managers in the world), wrote a letter, addressed to the CEOs of the companies that receive investments from his company, placing sustainability as a strategic focus of investments and the future of companies.

Nowadays, a large part of society gives importance to companies aligned with their values when choosing where they will work, which products to consume, which brands they have more affinity with and in which companies they will invest. Care for the environment, people and transparency are some of the factors analyzed. Furthermore, with the large presence of social media, it would be difficult for a company to escape unscathed if, for example, it employed slave labor or caused an environmental disaster, thus destroying its reputation and therefore its market value.

Currently in Brazil, several managers are choosing companies to compose the portfolios of their investment funds, prioritizing those that have their management models aligned with the ESG criteria and, of course, with good growth prospects. Some of these brokerage firms have launched equity investment funds on the market exclusively composed of companies that are part of the IBOVESPA and that follow the ASG criteria. Managers such as SulAmerica Investimentos, Veritas Capital, JGP and Fama, among others,

are some of the examples. Some even allocate part or all of the fees charged from investors to social projects. In fact, there has been a demand for financial products that meet these requirements for some time on the part of many investors.

As society in general, fund managers and investors are increasingly concerned about the issue, with a large movement of companies to implement these ESG practices, believing that this is the path to success. However, the main difficulty is that it is not enough to want, it is necessary that there is a change in culture, values, purpose, with a long-term vision that cannot change with the change of the CEO, for example. Companies have to understand that this is the only way to perpetuate their business and that there is no dichotomy between profitability and ESG criteria. It is a constant and evolving process that, combined with good levels of governance, will ensure that companies that implement such practices are more profitable in the future.

Harvard professor Dr. Robert Eccles led research that generated a paper in 2012 titled "The Impact of Corporate Sustainability on Organizational Processes and Performance" which showed evidence that companies with high sustainability significantly outperform their competitors in the long term, both in terms of the valuation of their shares and in accounting performance.

It is essential for market operators to inform their associates about the importance of ESG companies that today are part of the decision criteria of most consumers, of the most diverse products and services on the market. The idea of "responsible capitalism" has fueled a coercion on companies to adopt and deliver high standards of

performance in environmental, social and governance issues, whose main pressure points can be observed in relations with investors, consumers and civil society.

Investor enforcement has emerged as a result of individuals increasingly concerned that their investments must not only be financially sound, but also sustainable and socially beneficial and ethical.

The importance given by investors in relation to AGS practices can be observed, for example, through the actions carried out by “B3 SA – Brasil, Bolsa, Balcão”, responsible for the Brazilian stock exchange, which developed the Corporate Sustainability Index (“ISE”) to measure the average performance of the shares of companies that are committed to adopting sustainable policies. The ISE currently comprises shares of 30 companies that add up to R\$1.64 trillion in market value. In a comparative analysis between the performance of equity funds classified as Sustainable and Responsible Investment (“ISR”) and the performance of the Ibovespa, it is observed that the former presented a higher accumulated financial return in the last six years, including in the crisis period, which proves that investors are increasingly aware of the sustainable and responsible management of companies.

When dealing with consumer pressure, the change in their behavior must be observed, which in addition to demanding a quality product and/or service, began to question the social and environmental role of the companies from which they consume. Risks to companies’ reputation have increased with increasingly vigilant consumers, which forces them to also adjust the way they position themselves on ESG issues and practices.

Any type of practice that demonstrates a lack of responsibility with environmental and/or social issues is no longer considered acceptable, the negative impacts are immediate and extremely harmful to the companies’ reputation. Along with consumers, there are institutions of society that promote, by various means, campaigns denouncing the absence and/or failure of responsible conduct, whose reputational risks are immeasurable.

Likewise, responsible actions that create a positive impact on society are immediately recognized and applauded, becoming a model of corporate conduct to be expanded and copied. This is the case, for example, of what happened with the trainee program for leadership positions, exclusively for blacks, promoted by the company Magazine Luiza. Despite some criticisms, in our mistaken view, this measure was very well received and undoubtedly demonstrates the possibility of a corporation to contribute socially and positively, by promoting the inclusion of blacks in leadership positions, historically held by whites, and which is even aligned with the GT Technical Note on Race No. 001/2018, from the Public Labor Ministry.

It remains clear, therefore, that it is essential that companies start to integrate ESG issues in their management, if they want to remain attractive to investors, as well as to the general public.

REGULATION ON THE THEME

It is evident that, given the novelty of the subject in Brazil, that there is still an incipient regulation, with no explicit penalty from a legal point of view in what relates to non-compliance with such principles, which in itself imposes a legal challenge, as companies are

adapting to the implementation and compliance of the ESG regulations, which will necessarily lead to a review of the current regulatory norms.

So far, there is no legal rule that presents the 3 pillars of the AGS (environmental, social and governance) in a unified and specific way. However, it is possible to say that, both in Brazil and in the world, there are already general rules that allow and encourage companies to analyze these criteria in their operations and decision making.

In Brazil, for example, the provisions of the Corporate Law (Law nº 6.404/1976) can be interpreted in order to understand that companies must observe ESG factors in the decision-making process, by requiring in its article 116, sole § [4], that the controlling shareholder use its power of control to make the company realize its object and fulfill its social function. The State-Owned Companies Law (Law nº 13.303/2016), through its article 8, item IX, obliges public companies and mixed capital companies to prepare sustainability reports or integrated reports.

Within the scope of the financial system, Brazilian legislation is complemented by rules of the National Monetary Council ("CMN"), such as, for example, CMN Resolution No. resulted in the publication of the "Previc Guide to Best Investment Practices", which has as a novelty the introduction of a specific section to address ESG guidelines in investment management.

On environmental issues, Brazilian legislation has been incorporating international commitments, such as Law No. 12,187/09, which establishes the National Policy on Climate Change, and Law No.).

As market regulatory agents are

dynamic bodies such as AMBIMA, an independent and self-regulating element that operates in the financial market, launched in 2020 a guide for incorporating ESG aspects into investment analysis for banks and brokerages.

We also have the Central Bank of Brazil (BACEN), which also seeking to embrace the subject, launched its ASG agenda in 2020, thus being aligned with other Central Banks. In this agenda, aiming to guide the financial market, BACEN includes climate risk scenarios, seeking to develop a financial line of sustainable liquidity.

Last but not least, we have the National Bank for Economic and Social Development (BNDES), which recently created a line of financing, through the so-called BNDES Credit ASG, with free destination, where the primary requirement is that the company improve your sustainability indicators.

In principle, BNDES Credit ASG will be allocated to companies in specific segments: the wood chain focused on reforestation, manufacturers of equipment for the renewable energy and energy efficiency chain, mining, steel. These four sectors have great potential for improvement in environmental terms. The fifth sector, which has a greater potential for social than environmental impact, is that of small internet providers. Increasing connectivity is one of the goals of the BNDES' Triennial Plan 2020 -2022.

In the international scenario, the "Modern Slavery Act" of the United Kingdom, which aims for companies to take steps to ensure that slavery and human trafficking do not occur in their supply chains. Under this standard, companies with a global turnover of £36 million and operating in the United

Kingdom must publish a statement for each financial year, which must contain measures taken to ensure that slavery and human trafficking are not occur in the company or in the supply chain.

However, despite the existence of the aforementioned standards, in addition to others that deal in an isolated way with the pillars of the AGS, it must be recognized that we are still facing a timid regulatory environment, with informal and non-binding standards, and it is certain that such standards, mainly in line with public opinion, are guiding the way in which ESG integration is carried out by companies.

CONCLUSION

Today, in the corporate world, there is no possibility of rejecting or ignoring the application of ESG principles, compliance with its issues is something that cannot be ignored by companies. To attract investments and customers, engagement with the theme will be necessary and this will directly influence how companies will be seen by the market.

As explained, practice shows that there is still no rigid and binding standard to integrate ESG factors in the management of companies, and this integration is generally conducted by a set of good practices and principles that serve as a guide, and it is up to the manager /investor adapt them to their reality and needs.

However, even in an embryonic regulatory environment, failure to meet expectations related to ESG practices will result in legal challenges, as corporations will be exposed to various obligations, such as: reporting on ESG practices, reinterpretation of existing regulatory duties, as well as any need to present a defense in court, due to litigation based, for example,

on negligence in relation to its socio-environmental responsibilities.

In this way, the ESG purpose is to achieve commercial growth, also promoting sustainability, attention to society and good governance in companies. Therefore, the business adopts some measures to help and enhance these measures.

Considering the practical issue in the business environment, those who act according to ESG criteria and standards will be guided by these standards in decision-making and company policies. Thus, ethical values, social inclusion initiatives, ways of protecting and restructuring the environment, etc. can be adopted.

Some more skeptical and resistant may say that ESG is more a fad in the science of Management, but what no one can ignore is the fact that its emergence takes place from financial market initiatives, more specifically by banks and investment funds. able to allocate huge amounts to companies aligned with best practices in their management and means of production. It is a trend with real chances of lasting, as it aligns the interests of consumers, who favor companies with socio-environmental responsibility and investors who, in addition to being concerned with the image they pass on by investing in committed companies, manage to obtain a better positioning in the market and, consequently, a better return on capital invested, the same is true for companies.

In view of all this, increasingly, the adoption of ESG/ESG criteria has been providing sustainable benefits to companies' businesses, such as: brand appreciation, reputation improvement, risk reduction, talent attraction and the conquest of new

markets. These criteria, when adopted, reveal the sustainability of the business, indicate the solidity, transparency, and quality of the companies' performance, providing greater security for investors and consumers, who wish to contribute resources and establish commercial relationships with the enterprises.

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PUBLIC POLICY OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: EVOLUTIONS AND APPLICABILITY IN HEALTH IN THE STATE OF RIO DE JANEIRO.

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INTRODUCTION:

To understand the development of public policies aimed at People with Disabilities (PwD s), it is first necessary to understand the historical process of disability, its conceptual evolutions and the social movements around the issue. This article aims to bring a brief history of disability, as well as the construction of current public policies and the guarantee of the rights conquered along a difficult trajectory of exclusion and prejudice.

By following the historical context, we can observe changes in sociocultural behaviors and social movements that caused the transformations and paradigmatic concepts of what disability is today and how these changes gradually built and elaborated public policies aimed at People with Disabilities.

Despite historical data reporting the issue of disability since prehistory, a long period took place until the achievements of social rights.

In Brazil, the ratification of the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, in 2008, was the legal and historical landmark that consolidated the social perspective of disability, as well as the identification of who are the PwD in the country and the guarantee of the right to social protection of these subjects.

As a signatory to the United Nations (UN) Convention, Brazil has advanced in the implementation of public policies to guarantee the full and effective exercise of the legal capacity of people with disabilities in equal opportunities, valuing the role and choices of Brazilians with and without disabilities, with the launch of the National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Living without Limits through Decree 7,612, of November 17, 2011 (BRASIL, 2013). The proposal of Viver sem Limite is that the commitment assumed with the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities happens in people's lives, through the articulation of government policies for access to

education, social inclusion, health care and accessibility.

In the field of health, the Viver sem Limite Plan establishes the Care Network for People with Disabilities, aiming at the implementation, qualification and monitoring of rehabilitation actions in states and municipalities and their articulation between services, ensuring health promotion actions, early identification disability, disease prevention, treatment and rehabilitation. (BRAZIL, 2013).

The State of Rio de Janeiro, through the General Coordination for the Health of Persons with Disabilities , created its Care Network for Persons with Disabilities based on existing reference units, identifying them as possible services qualified to receive financial investment incentives. and costing. This made it possible, through the Ministry of Health, to enable the existing services, in addition to investment for construction, expansion and renovation. Such services were enabled by means of ordinances of the Ministry of Health, ensuring access and quality care to patients with physical, hearing, visual, intellectual disabilities and autism spectrum disorders (ASD), multiple disabilities and care for ostomy patients .

Complementing the advances in Public Policies aimed at People with Disabilities, in 2015 , LAW No. , under equal conditions, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by people with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship.

METHODOLOGY:

This article is categorized as a theoretical research with a qualitative approach, with an explanatory character within the historical-social context carried out by a bibliographic

review through books, scientific articles published in different national journals, laws, ordinances and decrees available in the databases online with a focus on the historical, social and rights analysis of people with disabilities.

DEVELOPMENT:

When researching the history of people with disabilities, we can find data from prehistoric life . According to Coma (1992) there are convictions that disabling diseases and physical disabilities are as old as life itself. Silva (1987) shows the existence of a complex system of beliefs and symbolisms involving individuals with disabilities . Continuing with the historical trajectory, in ancient Egypt the relationship between serious mental problems, physical disabilities and serious illnesses were associated with spiritual issues, where doctors believed that these conditions were caused by evil spirits, demons or sins of previous lives . Greece was considered the pioneer of medical care services for the general population and people with disabilities, when it implemented a system of care, initially aimed at the war maimed and later extended to other disabled people, regardless of the cause of the problem. (SILVA, 1987).

According to Roman law, the right to live was guaranteed only for children who did not present any signs of congenital malformation or serious diseases. Even with the right to legal infanticide, this practice was not carried out regularly, as it was up to the father to decide whether or not to execute it.

With Christianity and its creationist vision, the person with a disability also came to be seen as a creature of God and, therefore, possessing a soul and not deserving of punishment. Thus infanticide was no longer accepted.

In this way, the family and the church ensured care for the disabled person from a more pious and charitable perspective.

Renaissance period, between the 15th and 17th centuries, we had great advances based on a humanist philosophy and the first rights of men before society. The first signs of assistance to the PwD appeared. In England, King Henry VIII enacted the "Law of the Poor", by which all subjects were obliged to pay what was called the "charity fee", to continue the creation of hospital entities or organizations destined to the care of people with chronic problems or severely disabled for independent living (SILVA, 1987).

Society only adopted measures of assistance and protection for minorities and the marginalized, among them the PwD, in the 19th century, when in 1861, the United States began to guarantee housing and food to sailors and marines who acquired physical limitations. In 1867, the National Home for disabled volunteer soldiers was built in Philadelphia. (SILVA, 1987).

Some places in Europe also create specific places for the care and protection of PwD and the elderly and war disabled. We can cite as an example in 1872, in Denmark, the Society and Home for Cripples. Pioneering institution with the objective of helping people with disabilities to find an autonomous way to guarantee their livelihood, encouraging manual, artisanal and cooperative work among people with disabilities. (GARCIA, 2010).

Within the context of assistance programs and policies, we highlight the formation of the Welfare State in European countries after the Second World War, where policies aimed at serving the poor, the elderly, needy

children and people with disabilities began to be proposed, mainly war victims. In Great Britain, for example, in 1919, the Central Commission for the Care of the Disabled was created. (GARCIA, 2010).

The growing number of people with disabilities has become relevant in the internal politics of countries and with international proportions involving the United Nations (UN), as a consequence, on December 9, 1975, the Declaration of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities was approved, guaranteeing them in its third article the rights inherent to human equality. In 1981 the United Nations proclaimed The International Year of disabled Persons (International Year of Persons with Disabilities). (COSTA, 2008; FIGUEIRA, 2008).

Following the historical evolution, the UN approved the program of World Action for Persons with Disabilities (Resolution nº 37/52) on 12/03/1982, which has the principle of equal opportunities, guaranteeing access to the system for all disabled people. society – physical and cultural environment, housing, transport, social and health services, educational and work opportunities, cultural and social life, and even sports and leisure facilities, proclaiming the United Nations decade of disabled people, covering the years 1983 to 1992.

In Brazil, on the other hand, we can highlight the advance in the legal regulation of the social concept of disability in the first decades of the 21st century and with that, the adequacy of disability assessment for access to policies and services. The ratification of the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, in 2008, is the legal and historical landmark that consolidates the social perspective of disability, the definition of who the PwD are in the country and ensuring

the right to social protection of these subjects. (BARBOSA; DINIZ; SANTOS, 2010).

The social model appears in opposition to the biomedical model or the individual model of disability. For the biomedical model, disability is the result of a deviation in body functions and/or structures, and its treatment involves rehabilitation policies aimed at rescuing body functioning close to the functioning of those considered normal.

In the social model, people with disabilities suffer disadvantage because there is a culture of normality that privileges certain functionings to the detriment of others. By building the various social environments under an expectation of normality, the carnal order of humanity excludes the possibility of participation of people with disabilities. In this sense, disability is a system of inequality that must be addressed through inclusion and justice policies. (BARBOSA, BARROS, 2020)

Therefore, the social model considers that disability is an evolving concept and results from the interaction between people with disabilities and the barriers due to attitudes and the environment that prevent the full and effective participation of these people in society on an equal basis with others. (BRAZIL, 2009).

Aiming to advance in the implementation of public policies that would provide the full and effective exercise of the legal capacity of people with disabilities in equality of opportunities, valuing the protagonism and choices of Brazilians with and without disabilities, the National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Living without Limits, was launched through Decree 7,612, of November 17, 2011 (BRASIL, 2013). Emphasizing Brazil's

commitment to the prerogatives of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, ratified in Brazil with equivalent constitutional amendment. The proposal of Viver sem Limite is that the commitment assumed with the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities happens in people's lives, through the articulation of government policies for access to education, social inclusion, health care and accessibility.

Aiming to implement health actions determined by the Viver sem Limite Program, the federal government created in 2012 the Care Network for People with Disabilities, instituting the GM/MS Ordinance No. 793 of April 24, 2012 and No. 835 of April 25, 2012, legal framework for the beginning of the implementation of the Care Network for Persons with Disabilities (RCPD). Providing the implementation, qualification and monitoring of rehabilitation actions in states and municipalities and their articulation between services, ensuring health promotion actions, early identification of deficiencies, disease prevention, treatment and rehabilitation. (BRAZIL, 2013).

These ordinances were later updated by the MS/GM Consolidation Ordinance No. 3 of September 28, 2017, which consolidates the rules on the networks of the Unified Health System and No. 6, of September 28, 2017, which describes the financing rules and the transfer of federal resources for the actions and health services of the Unified Health System.

In parallel with the decrees and ordinances implemented in the field of health, in a dynamic process of consolidation of the social model of disability in Brazil, in 2015 the LAW No. which it describes in its article 1:

Art. 1 The Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities (Statute of Persons with Disabilities) is instituted, aimed at ensuring and promoting, on equal terms, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by persons with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and citizenship. (BRAZIL, 2015)

This article aims to highlight the experience of structuring the public policy of PwD in health, describing the process of structuring the Care Network for Persons with Disabilities (RCPD) in the State of Rio de Janeiro, where the care structure until 2011 was focused on the rehabilitation process, through the agreement of single modality rehabilitation services, that is, only in the physical, auditory and visual modalities and dispensing of orthoses, prostheses and means of locomotion, all funded by means of the medium and high financial ceiling complexity (MAC ceiling) (GOV. ERJ, 2020). As of 2013, in accordance with current ordinances, the structuring of the Network continued with municipal services that already performed some type of rehabilitation service and that were already recognized as a reference. The General Coordination of Health for People with Disabilities/DAPES/SAS/MS (CGSPD/MS) at the end of 2013, identified the possible services that could be enabled to receive financial investment and funding incentives, thus enabling the enabling of existing services, in addition to investment for construction, expansion and renovation. In December of the same year, ordinances were published referring to the qualification of these services and construction of new ones, as well as the structuring of the 1st State Conductor Group of the RCPD through CIB-RJ Resolution No. 2.457 of September 25, 2013. (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

RCPD's Mission is to implement Specialized Rehabilitation Centers (CER) and Orthopedic Workshops, thus ensuring access and quality care to patients with physical, hearing, visual, intellectual and autism spectrum disorders (ASD), multiple disabilities and care for ostomy patients.

Its Vision consists of including People with Disabilities in the provision of articulated and agreed care among the points of attention of the RCPD, stimulating their integration and their leading role in the economic, political and social context within the state of Rio de Janeiro.

And its Values are: Integrality of Care, Equity, Respect for the patient, Social inclusion, Autonomy, Innovation in health, its technical collaborators, supporters and managers of the three instances of the federation. It is important to highlight that the General State Health Coordination of PwD understands that the RCPD Vision should be revised according to its progress in the State of Rio de Janeiro. (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

The technical area and the coordination of the RCPD in the State of Rio de Janeiro, considers that in recent years, from the period of implementation of the RCPD to the present moment, that the services enabled in the Network model have matured and expanded their offer, adjusting their services aimed at for this logic, calibrating the quality of care for this public and, in a way, building the network flow between single modality services and CERs for the structuring of the care logic at the regional level (GOV, ERJ, 2020).

CONCLUSION:

Despite the long trajectory, the advances achieved, such as in the

establishment of a national policy for the integration of people with disabilities, in the legal constitution of general norms and basic criteria for the promotion of accessibility, there is still a huge gap between what the law determines and its effectiveness, as it is necessary to minimize and eliminate attitudinal barriers in order to overcome prejudice and exclusion.

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ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS: THE LIABILITY OF THE ADMINISTRATION FOR THE DAMAGES CAUSED

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ABSTRACT:

This article has as its scope the responsibility of the administration for the damages caused to the environment and the lack of awareness provided by the profiles of administrators that put them at risk due to the lack of planning and organization of the place. The general objective is to analyze the environmental conscience in the face of the administration's responsibility for the damages caused. It is a methodology with a qualitative approach, succeeding in the bibliographic research. Through this there were the analyzes of books, scientific articles, and internet materials consistent with the theme that, for such production, national authors of knowledge in administration and environment were reviewed environment. Therefore, it is concluded that environmental awareness is the most effective way that can serve as a challenge to administrators and managers who have the opportunity to embrace their implementations, inserting innovative strategies during their activities process. In short, with these actions, you will be able to contribute to the collectivity that operates, thus helping to build a space that can thrive.

Key words: Death; Mourning; Covid-19; Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, several business administrations internalize the concept of environmental awareness, which drives a concern with the conservation and preservation of the environment, considering that all this involves social, economic, and structural conditions. It is noticed that there is a plurality of complexities, which are listed in the responsibility for the damages caused, evidencing in the managerial dimensions, in terms of development, that converge in lousy administration.

This study was due to the environmental impacts and the lack of awareness that many business administrators do not consciously intensify the use of natural resources, socially and structurally proposing harmful ways linked to the environmental dimensions. This theme guides critical analyses, by inserting qualified scientific journals in the area of Administration, which may be productive for other academics from other areas of knowledge.

Thus, this study has as its general objective to analyze the environmental conscience in the face of the responsibility of the administration for the damages caused. So, the specific goals are: to understand the ecological conscience; understand management's responsibility for environmental damage, and analyze the importance of leadership in environmental awareness.

In this sense, the problem at hand is why is it necessary to have environmental awareness to avoid holding the administration accountable for the damage caused? This question will be answered in the course of the article, which emphasizes that raising awareness does not put the structure at risk, and an administrative action consistent with the integrity of the

environment can prevent problems causing degradation.

It is a methodology with a qualitative approach, succeeding in the bibliographic research that through this there were the analyzes of books, scientific articles and internet materials consistent with the theme that, for such production, national authors of knowledge in administration and environment were reviewed. environment.

ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS

The environment is everything that involves the existence of life on Earth, being part of an ecology that consists of a set of chemical, social, biological, and physical elements that bring indirect or direct effects on human beings. In addition, there is a natural system composed of microorganisms, flora, fauna, atmosphere, rocks, and soils, among others, that are part of environmental phenomena. It is essential to highlight that man is the significant influencer of nature, which can establish impacting processes on the planet.

Historically, environmental processes have been impacted since the emergence of the Industrial Revolution because industries were the great precursors of atmospheric pollution and exploitation. In addition, urbanization several years has dramatically intensified the production of waste, emerging as a worrying factor in humanity's relationship with natural resources (PACHECO et al., 2019). Through all this, environmental awareness emerged, which consists of understanding the space where man is inserted.

However, "it seems then that we are in a historical moment of fundamental importance for the acquisition of a

different awareness of human relations with the natural and social environment” (DORO; SPAZZIANI, 2022, p. 21-22), which is why, the search in the analysis of environmental structures, had an intention that led to the understanding of transforming the concepts and practices for a better environment.

In general, environmental awareness came to be understood due to environmental causes, considering the short, medium, and long term impacts. It encompasses the pollution generated by various human actions and demanded resources. With this, to have a conscience in the sense of improvement, it is necessary to have a closer relationship with the environment, which may awaken some conceptions about the reflexes of nature itself. Even because all knowledge is generated in practice and can bring positive effects.

The emergence of environmental issues and climate change and the emergence of movements that are increasingly aware that we are in fact experiencing a serious problem that can jeopardize the future of the human species, brings to the fore the way in which society is actually informed about environmental issues. The emergency to solve environmental problems calls for citizens to be active and environmentally “literate”, and it makes sense to promote a “capacity” or competence in citizens, which is Environmental Literacy (MORENO; MAFRA, 2022, p. 66) .

However, raising awareness among human beings requires external factors that influence daily habits, that is, the relationships between the environment and organisms. Therefore, it can be said that preservation and human awareness of the ecological system depend on participation and understanding, involving everyone in a society through

activities that contribute to general conservation, and education through training in environmental awareness.

1.1. BRIEF CONCEPTS

The word conscientize means a conscious act linked to the human attitude, which conveys something to obtain information. In addition, awareness is a process that consists of consciously, where the individual acquires knowledge and doing, bringing a meaning that, in general, can get its own benefits, that is, an informed human being capable of dealing with the most diverse situations. Criticism, obtaining experiences or insights that suit you on a particular subject.

About environmental awareness, it is the creation or transformation of a critical sense about the damage caused to the environment, due to exploitation caused damage, resulting in the precision of human care. It can be said that it is an introspective process that requires the individual to acquire thoughts that aim at the rationality of conservation (HARTMANN, 2010). When talking about this subject, he inserts that in Brazil, there are several educational means to promote the conscientious issue of nature, for example, legislation, and warnings, among others.

[...] the fragmentation and sectoralization of administrative action, insufficiently compensated by coordination and integration mechanisms, and the inadequacy of territorial organization, involving types of territorial cuts, division of responsibilities between them and definition of the relationships between the different levels, in mechanisms view of the project of an integrated management of resources and natural environments.

Environmental awareness is a form of

conscious education, which represents fundamental instruments in the form of thinking for possible transformations of the damage caused to the environment. In addition, environmental degradation is a complex factor that requires educational practices with a transforming function, such as, for example, individuals who are aware of actions that make it essential for a better and sustainable world (KLOETZEL, 2017).

By Ramos et al. (2021, p. 85), environmental problems arise from,

[...] the fragmentation and sectoralization of administrative action, insufficiently compensated by coordination and integration mechanisms, and the inadequacy of territorial organization, involving types of territorial cuts, division of responsibilities between them and definition of the relationships between the different levels, in view of the project of an integrated management of resources and natural environments.

Therefore, the primary function of environmental awareness is to show the relevance of the various ramifications that make human beings aware of maintaining a balance since, for sustainable practices, accountability is needed, which becomes broad, as it consists of various sectors that influence the structuring of the environment, also considering the involvement of managers both environmentally and administratively, this because, being linked to the conservation of places and natural resources.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND MANAGEMENT MANAGEMENT

The environment is structured in impacts due to procedures that meet expectations and needs for an associated societal improvement. Previously, the problems are implanted due to the

operationalization of the enterprises established by the managers, which come through instruments and plans that impact the spaces, as well as mitigate complexity that degrades the natural resources; such identifications consist of the activities, services, and productions that negatively generate degradations. However, "in all segments of this legal discipline, the aspect of preventing environmental damage stands out" (BENJAMIN, 2006, p. 14).

However, organizational performance generates several positive and negative aspects, which play an essential role in managing development models that require rational management, mainly when referring to responsibilities around natural resources (BORTOLASO, 2021). The administrator is responsible mainly for minimizing environmental impacts and promoting a balance that is in accordance with the productive needs that characterize the maintenance of the place.

As Benjamin (2006, p. 01) explains:

[...] environmental protection is directly related to the issue of administrative discretion. Environmental protection, over time, has always been at the expense of the environment. More and more restraints are imposed on the administrator, always with the aim of strengthening his preservationist vein, weakening his eco-mutilator side.

In this context, the administrator must have a strategic dimension to plan development without impacting the environment. Furthermore, it is necessary to maintain and implement environmental policies that promote sustainability, characterized by actions and procedures consistent with the protection and preservation of the place.

The integrity of physical environments and social groups depends on the monitoring and controlling the fundamental instruments that bring the quality of services (AROEIRA, 2022).

Therefore, the administration of managers is of mere importance because it consists of activities and services which are performed in an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary way to achieve positive results about the structure of the place (BARBIERI; SILVA, 2020). However, a good administrator always has a holistic view to reducing environmental impacts caused by human action and needs administrative rationality that minimizes the damage caused.

THE RESPONSIBILITY OF THE ADMINISTRATION GIVEN TO ENVIRONMENTAL DAMAGE

As seen, environmental awareness brings significant factors when it is conducted with good management. The administrative responsibility about the environment is based on the damage caused, having as content in art. 70 of Law No. 9,605/98, providing for the administrative infraction, in which every action and omission is considered an environmental crime. As a general rule, other legal instruments mention the offending agent for imposing a fine, consisting of criminal and civil liability (SILVA, 2007).

It should be noted that Garcia et al. (2020) clarified that, "because of the exploratory activity, there is a concern about the damage that can occur to the environment and how the repair could occur if it occurred"; thus, there can be means for accountability over fall in the face of the administrator.

Administrative responsibility results from infractions of the administrative

rules that, consequently, the administrator is subject to punishment, warning, fine, or interdiction of the activity. Therefore, the damage caused to the environment becomes significant, which, during the year, becomes responsible for goods that affect the community, taking into account that all this happened due to the lack of planning and organization, which they are fundamental for avoiding future consequences.

Provisions for environmental crimes are added, inserting any ecological damage resulting from mismanagement; that is, for infractions to the environment, administrative sanctions are consigned to those individuals, this is because, the prescriptions that compete in accountability will consist according to the disciplinary norm (BLIACHERIS; FERREIRA, 2012). It is worth mentioning that every manager or administrator is responsible for preserving and managing their heritage, attributing to environmental conservation through good planning and organization.

In this way, it can be said that responsibility in the administrative sphere and punishment for damages caused to the environment consists even, then, of more significant harm, for requiring repair, sometimes tricky, for taking time to achieve a restoration (CHIAVENATO, 2000). Therefore, having administrative awareness about environmental appeals, processing development and organization will bring greater credibility and visibility, as it does not harm natural resources.

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADMINISTRATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Analyzing the whole context, it is understood that administrative

environmental awareness is nothing more than an entirely preserved and organized environment. In addition, the search for information is a factor that keeps any administrator or manager up to date since the combination of its attribution in a conscientious way brings alert to the risks and impacts that damage not only structural but to the collectivity. It is noticed that there is vitality throughout the administrative process, which can present measures and solutions that can be taken to reduce the causing effects.

The role of environmental awareness in the administrative relationship is to create sustainable thinking in order to reduce the impacts caused to the environment. That is, when a process is carried out within a company, mentalities with shared decisions can occur in the way of thinking with other individuals, whether friends, or employees, among others. In addition, it is essential to consider a preserved space or place because putting simple measures into practice can make a difference, mainly avoiding responsibility for the illegality of damages caused to the environment (SOUZA FILHO, 2020).

The Ministry of the Environment has structured six thematic axes for the importance of implementation in administrative services, which they have: The “rational use of natural resources and public goods; management of generated waste; quality of life in the work environment; awareness and training of servers; sustainable public procurement; sustainable constructions,” which are used as programs to maintain the sustainability and conservation of the site (MMA, 2022).

Taking good care of a company or space is to think that the way other people treat the environment is to

becoming aware of the need for change to avoid environmental impacts. Some economic and social transformations are fundamental for ecological preservation, not least because many people already have a sharp vision for conscious consumption. For example, sustainable buildings, and concern for energy savings, among other aspects. It should be noted that, in administration, environmental awareness happens progressively. However, attitudes can reduce environmental damage.

Environmental awareness in the management relationship aims to transform the agents’ habits in implementing responsibility in their administrative functions. By the way, attitudes and practices that reduce the wear and tear of activities can prevent the unruly form that causes the environment. Sustainable actions in services, seek adoption for new patterns of consumption and reduction, among others. This is an awareness that managers or administrators can harbor for the importance of such issues.

Today, there is a need for organizations to work with policies aimed at environmental issues, showing that the market gains provided by this new administrative approach can mean the permanence of these companies in their market, in addition to enabling the gain of new markets (FRACASSO, 2011, p. 24).

Therefore, encourage criteria and principles that involve environmental implementation in routine activities, encouraging and promoting the adoption and implementation of actions consisting of responsibility for the environment, envisioning the collectivity and personal engagement for everyone involved in the services.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing everything exposed in this article, it was observed that environmental awareness is directly linked to sustainability, giving meaning to its actions and practices that preserve resources. It is understood that making human beings aware can influence different habits in everyday life, passing a segment that raises participation and sensitivity that contribute to the conservation of space. It is noted that lifestyle changes bring attitudes that differentiate the routine socially, collectively, and individually.

In this way, it is clear that the primary function of environmental awareness is to branch out and maintain a balance between people, using in a concertizing way everything that involves their needs. Therefore, observing sustainable practices, it was understood that there is a precision for accountability, broadening the most varied influence regarding the structuring of the environment. So, it became clear that managers are primarily responsible for keeping their administrative form linked to the conservation of the site.

However, environmental impacts are factors with numerous problems, and can thus cause a process that holds managers responsible during their administrative functions, for harming the environment. With this, it is suggested that a strong orientation towards the segments of customs, habits, among other aspects that are highly protected and valued during the permanence of collective and individual activities. Therefore, innovations and cooperation between individuals present themselves, therefore, as the most promising alternatives for site conservation.

That said, it is noted that administrative

responsibility in relation to damage caused to the environment is conditioned by the use of activities, goods, among others for the benefit of the community, which can be punished with sanctions or fines, in cases of infractions. It follows that, in the event of such action, within the limits of their respective ones, they may be enshrined in the legislation that pertains to the case, individually, since it is observed that the behaviors affect or can affect the entire structure of the environment.

Therefore, it is concluded that environmental awareness is the most effective way that can serve as a challenge to administrators and managers who have the opportunity to embrace with their implementations, inserting innovative strategies during their activities process. In short, with these actions you will be able to contribute to the collectivity that operates, thus helping to build a space that can thrive.

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